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D5.5 – Map of potential for PM(T) substitution in one high-stake sector

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Executive Summary

Substitution of hazardous chemicals is a central objective of the European Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability and the Zero Pollution Ambition of the Green Deal. In this context, substances that are Persistent, Mobile, and Toxic (PMT), or very Persistent and very Mobile (vPvM), are recognised as posing long-term and widespread environmental and human health risks. The effective identification and substitution of such substances remain, however, a significant regulatory and technical challenge.

This report, produced under the H2020 PROMISCES project, explores the potential for substitution of PMT and vPvM substances. Leveraging a dataset covering more than 120 000 substances and drawing on multiple sources of information—including REACH registration dossiers, the NORMAN SusDat database, and dedicated substance-level studies—the report applies three distinct analytical approaches:

1. A sectoral analysis based on REACH use data to assess the distribution of PMT/vPvM substances across **product categories** and **sectors of use**;
2. A **functional use analysis focused on surfactants** from the NORMAN database, using classifications derived from the results of the project;
3. A **substance-specific case study on benzotriazoles**, a family of compounds with high production volumes and confirmed PMT properties.

Across all approaches, the study applies a tiered scoring system to assess persistence, mobility and toxicity, accounting for the level of confidence associated with different types of data (experimental, predicted, or absent).

Key Findings:

- **Sectoral Insights:** Analysis of REACH data showed that PMT substances are broadly distributed across sectors, but no sector emerged as uniquely or disproportionately affected. However, sectors such as fine chemicals manufacturing, food production, water treatment, and construction may be of interest for future targeted assessments.
- **Data Gaps and Limitations:** The scarcity of experimental data severely constrains the robust classification of substances, especially for persistence and mobility. As a result, the identification of PMT/vPvM substances often relies on predicted data, with varying degrees of confidence.
- **High Proportion of Potentially Concerning Substances:** Conservative modelling scenarios suggest that at least 37% of surfactants assessed (over 30,000 substances) may be classified as PMT or vPvM. However, none could be classified as such based solely on experimental data.
- **Limited Identification of Safer Alternatives:** Despite a large initial dataset, no surfactants could be confidently identified as non-persistent, non-mobile and non-toxic based on available data. The same type of results was obtained in the case study on Benzotriazoles. This unexpected result underlines the complexity of avoiding "regrettable substitution" and the limitations of current data sources in enabling the identification of truly safer alternatives. This also highlights the importance that should be given to the study of non-chemical alternatives for the substitution of substances of concern.
- **Priority Substances Identified:** The study highlights 455 surfactants as priority candidates for further investigation, based on robust data for two hazard properties and reliable modelled data for the third. An additional 8 substances may warrant particular scrutiny due to their potential classification as vPvM.

- Benzotriazoles Case Study: The detailed analysis of benzotriazoles confirms their widespread use and significant hazard potential. Some benzotriazoles are already listed or under assessment for regulatory action due to their PMT or PBT properties. For uses as UV-absorbers or UV-filters, the analysis illustrates the difficulty to identify better alternatives. For uses as corrosion inhibitor, the case study underscores the value of combining high-level screening with substance-specific evaluations to support substitution efforts.

Conclusions and Recommendations:

- The study highlights the potential of systematic, large-scale assessments for prioritising substances for substitution. However, it also reveals the urgent need for more comprehensive and reliable data, particularly on persistence and mobility, to support regulatory and industrial decision-making.
- Predictive modelling tools are useful but must be applied with caution. In the absence of sufficient experimental data, reliance on conservative assumptions may lead to overly broad lists of substances flagged for concern, potentially limiting the practical value of prioritisation.
- There is no evidence, based on current data, that surfactants exist which can be confidently classified as both effective and safer alternatives (i.e., non-PMT/vPvM). This calls for enhanced research efforts, including targeted experimental studies and sector-specific engagement, to identify and validate truly sustainable substitution pathways.
- The [PROMISCES Decision Support Framework](#), including its PMT Assessment and Diagnosis Modules, offers a promising basis for operationalising the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework and supporting future substitution strategies (See also recommendation #8 in [Deliverable D5.8](#)).

Overall, this report underscores the complexity of chemical substitution in the case of PMT/vPvM substances and points to critical data and methodological needs that must be addressed to achieve more effective, evidence-based substitution policies.

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List of Abbreviations

CE	Circular Economy
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design
CEC(s)	Contaminant(s) of emerging concern
CSs	Case studies
DSF	Decision Support Framework
EC	European Commission
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EQS	Environmental Quality Standards
EU	European Union
iPM(T)	Industrial Persistent, Mobile and potentially Toxic
KEMI	Swedish Chemicals Agency
Koc	Organic carbon-water partition co-efficient.
N/A	Not available/not applicable
NORMAN	Network of reference laboratories, research centres and related organisations for monitoring of emerging environmental substances
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PM(T)	Persistent, Mobile and potentially Toxic
PMT	Persistent, Mobile and Toxic
POPs	Persistent organic pollutants
REACH	Registration, evaluation, authorisation and restriction of chemicals
RIVM	Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design
US EPA CPDat	United States Environmental Protection Agency Chemical and Products Database
vPvM	very Persistent very Mobile
WWTPs	Wastewater treatment plants

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1 Introduction

1.1 Substitution is an essential part of chemical risk management policies

The substitution principle is a fundamental aspect of the EU Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability and reflects the goal of achieving a non-toxic environment. This principle involves replacing hazardous chemicals with safer alternatives, a key objective of current European chemicals policy (EC, 2020).

The European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) defines the substitution principle as “the replacement or reduction of hazardous substances in products or processes by less hazardous or non-hazardous substances, or by achieving an equivalent functionality via technological or organisational measures.”

European chemicals regulation is primarily organised based on the intended use of chemicals. The substitution principle is included in European regulation for plant protection products (pesticides), mainly regulated under the Plant Protection Product Regulation (EC) 1107/2009 (PPPR), for biocides under the Biocidal Products Regulation (EU) No. 528/2012 (BPR) and industrial chemicals under Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006 for the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation, and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) in the European Union. Additionally, other chemical regulations, such as Regulation (EC) No. 1223/2009 concerning cosmetic products, Regulation (EC) 1935/2004 on materials and articles intended to come into contact with food, and Regulation (EC) 726/2004 on medicinal products for human and veterinary use, establish conditions for substance approval.

Despite the established regulatory framework, the substitution of hazardous chemicals has to become more efficient (EC, 2021). This underscores the need to identify the chemicals of concern and expedite the adoption of safer alternatives (EC, 2023).

1.2 Substituting Persistent and Mobile Chemicals: What is at stake?

PM(T) substances, including degradation products, are persistent in the environment, highly soluble in water, and, therefore, easily transported through it. Additionally, because of their physicochemical properties, PM(T) substances are poorly removed in conventional treatment processes, threatening European drinking water supplies and food production.

Chemical persistence is a major environmental issue, as natural ecosystem barriers fail to eliminate these substances. This results in their accumulation in water and nutrient cycles (Reemtsma et al., 2016). They remain during water treatment and food production, posing significant human and ecological health risks.

Identifying and prioritising PM(T) substances for further study is essential for evaluating their risks. There is a growing scientific consensus that the persistence of chemical substances, regardless of any other property, poses a significant environmental and human health problem (Cousins et al., 2019). In other words, persistence alone is sufficient for managing chemicals, as persistent chemicals can accumulate in the environment or in human organs, leading to concentrations at which even mildly hazardous chemicals can cause the possibility of long-term effects on ecosystems and human health.

Persistent substances accumulate in the environment and bioaccumulate within trophic chains, therefore possibly leading to significant ecological and health impacts. Further, as these chemicals enter the food web, they are taken up by organisms at lower trophic levels, which may not be able to break down or eliminate these substances, increasing concentration as higher trophic levels consume them, a phenomenon known as biomagnification.

This accumulation of persistent substances in organisms can have profound, often detrimental, effects on their health. Chronic exposure to these chemicals can lead to numerous health issues, including reproductive and developmental anomalies, immune system dysfunction, and endocrine disruption. These impacts may not be immediately observable and can take years to manifest, making them particularly challenging to measure and assess. For instance, subtle changes in reproductive rates or immune responses may not be linked directly to chemical exposure without comprehensive long-term studies.

Furthermore, persistent chemicals can affect individual organisms, entire populations, and ecosystems. As these substances circulate through the food web, they can compromise the health of apex predators, including humans, who rely on these ecosystems for food. Thus, the implications of chemical persistence extend beyond localised contamination, posing a widespread threat to biodiversity, food security, and public health.

1.3 Complementing Substitution with the Safe and Sustainable by Design Framework (SSbD)

As the push for safer and more sustainable chemicals intensifies, effective substitution strategies become paramount, particularly when dealing with persistent and toxic substances that pose significant challenges to innovation and environmental safety. Substances classified as persistent, mobile, and toxic (PMT) or very persistent and very mobile (vPvM) are often difficult to replace due to their widespread use ([Deliverable D5.1](#)) and inherent properties (Reemtsma et al., 2016). The “Safe and Sustainable by Design” (SSbD) framework emerges as an important tool in this context, offering a proactive and voluntary approach to integrate safety, sustainability, and circularity into developing chemicals and materials.

Announced through the Commission Recommendation (EU) 2022/2510, the SSbD framework emphasizes the importance of identifying hazardous substances and provides [methodological guidance](#) and tools, such as the PARC [SSbD Toolbox](#), that collects tools and models for each stage of the framework to facilitate the assessment and prioritisation of these challenging substances for substitution (European Commission: Joint Research Centre, Caldeira, et al., 2022; European Commission: Joint Research Centre et al., 2024; European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC), n.d.).

The PROMISCES project has developed tools and delivered information complementary to the tools in the PARC SSbD Toolbox, which are included in the PROMISCES Decision Support Framework (DSF). Relevant parts of the DSF in this regard are the *PMT Assessment*, the *Prevention and Diagnosis* modules. These modules can be used as a fit-for-purpose tool to identify (potential) PMT and vPvM substances and their sector of use. This is deemed important as the first step of the SSbD approach is to focus on the intrinsic properties of chemicals and materials and identify those that are inherently hazardous. PMT and vPvM substances are within the “most harmful substances” category (according to the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability) that should be prioritised for substitution, re-designed to reduce their adverse effects, or could be allowed only in uses proven essential to society. Furthermore, the SSbD framework acknowledges that available information could be limited and recommends using diverse information sources, like New Approach Methodologies (NAMs), to get data and generate knowledge. In the Diagnosis and PMT Assessment modules, different types of information sources are used (such as QSARs, etc.), which allow evaluation of whether the PMT/vPvM endpoint is likely to be fulfilled or not.

1.4 Objective and outline of the report

The objective of this report is to examine to what extent the data compiled during the PROMISCES project, covering more than 120,000 substances (Sardi et al., 2024), can contribute to substitution-related challenges, either by identifying particularly affected sectors of use or by comparing possible alternatives.

Following a second section that outlines the methodological framework of this report, Sections 3, 4 and 5 present three distinct approaches aimed at assessing, based on the results produced within the PROMISCES project, the extent to which it is possible to identify substances for which substitution should be considered, as well as the safest alternatives.

More specifically, Section 3 is a study of use-related information contained in REACH registration dossiers. Section 4 focuses on substances associated with the same technical function within the NORMAN databases, namely surfactants. Section 5 provides a more detailed analysis of the uses of benzotriazoles, their hazardous properties, and those of their potential alternatives.

2 Methodology and followed approach

Most of the work presented in this report is based on data and methodologies presented in [Deliverable D5.1](#) (Sardi et al., 2024). For details on score calculation, benchmark values and classification, please refer to the methodology described in the aforementioned deliverable. The universe of the chemical substances that is screened in this report is based on the NORMAN SusDat database¹ downloaded in June 2024, which included 120 416 substances. No curation was done to this database, which is already in a workable format.

2.1 Scores and substances' classification

For each substance, scores between 0 and 1 were calculated to characterize their persistence, mobility, and toxicity properties, individually. Multiple scores were computed for a given property depending on whether they were based on experimental or predicted data. Briefly, three scenarios accounting for data quality and are proposed:

- Conservative Scenario: Select the highest score based on predicted data.

¹ <https://www.norman-network.com/nds/susdat/>

- Average Scenario: Calculates the average score based on all the data sources for predicted data².
- Robust Scenario: Select the highest score based on experimental data.

For the substance classification, the following thresholds were used:

- nP, nM (n stands for not): scores lower than 0,33
- P, M: scores higher or equal to 0,33 and lower than 0,5
- vP, vM: scores higher or equal to 0,5
- nT (average and conservative scenario): scores lower than 0,33
- T (average and conservative scenario): scores higher than 0,33
- T (robust scenario): if any of the criteria from Figure 1 is covered, the substance is classed as toxic.

Figure 1 : Criteria for classification as T (toxic)

² In general, the definition adopted in the project for the average scenario is based on the following principle: “the average score is based on at least two data sources for predicted data”. However, as will be shown later in this study, this definition can be ambiguous when only a single data source is available. According to the general definition, in such cases, the average scenario does not yield a result. For the sake of clarity in the reasoning, we occasionally (see Part 5) use a simplified approach in this report, referring to the average scenario as the mean of all predicted data, even when there is only one data point. In such cases, the average and conservative scenarios become equivalent. This caveat is reiterated throughout the report.

The substance classification considers all the potential combinations of the previous categories. For instance, a substance is classified as vPMT under the robust scenario if $P_{\text{robustscore}} > 0,5$, $0,33 \leq M_{\text{robustscore}} < 0,5$, and any of the criteria from Figure 1 is covered. A substance is classified as PT when $0,33 \leq P_{\text{robustscore}} < 0,5$, any of the criteria from Figure 1 is covered but no data is available on M.

2.2 Data treatment and visualisation

Data analysis and scoring calculations were made in Python using Jupyter Notebook. Visualisations were made using the *Plotly* library. The working database, the scripts used for merging and cleaning it, and the ones for calculating the scores of substances are available on [Zenodo](#) (Sardi et al., 2024).

2.3 Information and data on chemical uses

Various sources can be explored to map the uses of the substances. In this report three approaches are explored.

The first one consisted in using the registered uses information in the REACH registration dossiers. Using the available data, several analyses were done to describe the number of substances per sector of use or product category, their tonnage, and their classification (see also D5.1, Sardi et al., 2024).

In the second one, the use groups were derived from the NORMAN substance source lists. The NORMAN SusDat database³ is constructed by aggregating diverse substance lists. These lists often group substances either from the same chemical group (such as PFAS), those that have a similar impact (e.g., endocrine-disrupting chemicals, EDCs), or those that are associated with similar applications (e.g. plastic additives). By using the labels of these source lists, we can infer the potential uses of the substances. Table 17 in Annexes provides the complete list of sources (as of June 2024) and the proposed categorisation of use groups.

The third approach is more traditionally based on a literature review of scientific publications and reports, as well as an internet search, particularly using chemical product information platforms.

3 Analysis of substitution challenges based on use data provided by the REACH regulation

3.1 Uses data registered in REACH registration dossiers

In this section, ECHA's Sector of Use and Product Category information required within the substances registration dossiers are used. Product category (PC) and Sector of use (SU) data were retrieved from the ECHA website on 07/2022 (See Annexes, Tables 17 to 19) and incorporated within the working data set available at Sardi et al., 2024. The Pc and SU categories are market descriptors, and according to ECHA's Chapter Guidance on Information Requirements and Chemical Safety

³ <https://www.norman-network.com/nds/susdat/>

Assessment Chapter R.12 (European Chemicals Agency, 2015), the SU describes the market and the sector of economy where the use takes places, while the PC describes in which types of chemical products (i.e., substances as such or in mixtures) the substance is finally contained when it is supplied to, and used by, end-users e.g. detergents, paints.

After revising ECHA registration dossiers, the proportion of substances within the SusDat database with Sector of Use and Product category data was ~4,5%: within the dataset, 5453 substances had SU information, each assigned to one or more sectoral use categories, while 5372 had PC information. As presented in Figure 2, The product category and sector of use with the highest number of substances are respectively PC 19: Intermediates and SU 9: Manufacture of fine chemicals⁴.

Figure 2 : Number of substances per product category (top) and per Sector of use (down)

⁴ PC and SU nomenclatures are available in Table 188 and Table 199 in section 8. Annexes

3.2 Classification of substances per SU and PC

Based on substance classification and available data on their sectors of use and product categories, we attempted to develop a general mapping. The objective is to assess whether certain sectors appear to be more specifically affected by issues related to persistence, mobility, and toxicity.

Under the three proposed scenarios, we explored the distribution of substances according to their classification (e.g., vPMT, PT, vP, nP) across different PCs and SUs (see Annexes, Table 17 to 19). The substance repartition among classification categories is summarized using heatmaps presented in Figure 3 and Figure 4. The figures illustrate the number of substances per PC and SU, allowing a comparative view of how different PMT categories are distributed across industrial and commercial sectors. The x-axis represents the uses, the y-axis displays the classification categories, and the colour scale indicates the number of substances. We opted to use the number of substances as a metric rather than the percentage of PM(T) or vPvM substances within a sector of use. This approach provides an indication of the amount of work and substance evaluation required if a full high-stake sector is selected for substitution. The figure shows the three scenarios from top to bottom: conservative, average, and robust.

Comparison of PM(T) Substances per Product Category Across Scenarios

Figure 3 : Heatmap representing the number of substances per product category (PC) group under three classification scenarios: conservative, average, and robust. The colour intensity represents the count of substances within each category. Each heatmap is accompanied by its legend, ensuring a clear interpretation of data across scenarios. Data are ordered by product category for consistency and comparability.

Comparison of PM(T) Substances per Sector of Use Across Scenarios

- SU1: Agriculture, forestry and fishing
- SU2a: Mining (without offshore industries)
- SU2b: Offshore industries
- SU4: Manufacture of food products
- SU5: Manufacture of textiles, leather, fur
- SU6a: Manufacture of wood and wood products
- SU6b: Manufacture of pulp, paper and paper products
- SU7: Printing and reproduction of recorded media
- SU8: Manufacture of bulk, large scale chemicals (including petroleum products)
- SU9: Manufacture of fine chemicals
- SU10: Formulation [mixing] of preparations and/or re-packaging (excluding alloys)
- SU11: Manufacture of rubber products
- SU12: Manufacture of plastics products, including compounding and conversion
- SU13: Manufacture of other non-metallic mineral products, e.g. plasters, cement,
- SU14: Manufacture of basic metals, including alloys
- SU15: Manufacture of fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment
- SU16: Manufacture of computer, electronic and optical products, electrical equipment,
- SU17: General manufacturing, e.g. machinery, equipment, vehicles, other transport equipment
- SU18: Manufacture of furniture
- SU19: Building and construction work
- SU20: Health services
- SU23: Electricity, steam, gas water supply and sewage treatment,
- SU24: Scientific research and development

Figure 4: Heatmap representing the number of PM(T) substances per sector of use (SU) group under three classification scenarios: conservative, average, and robust. The colour intensity represents the count of substances within each category. Each heatmap is accompanied by its legend, ensuring a clear interpretation of data across scenarios. Data are ordered by sector of use for consistency and comparability.

The first observation is that only limited experimental data exist for P and M. Without experimental data for persistence and mobility, the robust scenario allows classification only concerning toxicity. Under this scenario, the SU9 (Manufacture of fine chemicals) sector and product category PC19 (Intermediates) contain the highest number of toxic substances. At a lower order of magnitude, SU8 (Manufacture of bulk, large scale chemicals) and SU12 (Manufacture of plastic products), as well as PC0 (Other), PC15 (Non-metal surface treatment products), PC21 (Laboratory chemicals), PC32

(Polymer preparations), and PC39 (Cosmetic and personal care products) are the most affected sectors.

The average scenario leads to similar results in terms of identifying priority sectors. For this scenario, the fact that the PROMISCES results on predicted mobility are in most cases based on a single model⁵ results in a low level of information regarding mobility. However, this scenario highlights that a large number of substances are classified as very persistent. For instance, 1877 substances are classified as vPT in PC19, and 3071 in SU9.

In the case of the conservative scenario, classification based on mobility is possible, and the categories vPvMT, vPMT, and vPnMT are the most frequently represented. There is a certain degree of homogeneity of classifications among sectors, with the exception of SU9 and SU8. Homogeneity is also observed across classifications within a given sector: SU9 is the sector with the highest number of substances in all classification categories. This analysis therefore does not support the identification of a classification that is more specifically associated with a particular sector. The conclusions are generally similar regarding product categories.

3.3 Tonnages, classification per SU and PC

REACH registration dossiers may include quantitative use data, referred to as tonnage bands. These represent orders of magnitude of the quantities of substances manufactured or imported in Europe, following a logarithmic scale: from 1 to 10 tonnes, 10 to 100 tonnes, 100 to 1000 tonnes, etc.

Various analyses of these data were conducted as part of this study. We sought to examine sectors of use and product categories with the highest tonnages, those with the highest tonnage per registered substance, and to compare these data with PMT classifications.

However, the decision was made not to present these results in this report, as they did not allow for the identification of sectors or product categories specifically associated with issues of persistence, mobility, and toxicity.

This is due to the high level of uncertainty inherent in the available data. In addition to the wide intervals of the tonnage bands, which are sometimes incomplete (e.g., only the minimum tonnage is reported), it is not possible to distribute the tonnages across the various sectors and product categories.

For example, a substance registered with a tonnage band of 1000 to 10 000 tonnes may be associated with 12 different product categories, without any indication as to which category accounts for the largest share. Various working assumptions were tested: distributing the average tonnage evenly across all 12 categories, assigning the maximum tonnage to each, etc. These assumptions had a significant impact on the results, but their validity could not be reliably assessed.

⁵ By definition, the average scenario relies on at least two data sources

Verifying them would require a substantial effort, analysing each substance and each use individually, based on information not consolidated in databases (e.g., grey literature, scientific publications) or through interviews with producers or users. This lies outside the scope of the present work.

Nonetheless, the remainder of the report will show that tonnage band data can be useful when the focus is placed on a specific substance or group of substances.

3.4 Average scores per PC and SU

This last section aims to refine the previous analyses by identifying which sectors of use and product categories have the highest averaged persistency, mobility, toxicity and emission scores. P and M scores were averaged for each sector of use and product category and represented in scatter plots (Fig. 5 Figure 5). These score aggregations were done using conservative scores, which, according to D.5.1, are the higher scores available for each substance. Please note that these are not the average scenario scores, but the average per PC or SU of the conservative scenario. The Kemi-score is also included.

The Kemi score, developed by Stellan Fisher (Swedish Chemicals Agency, KEMI), indicates an exposure index and is based on three different components (independent datasets):

1. The annual tonnage (AT index) is calculated using tonnage data available in the REACH database.
2. Measure for release during use (use index, UI), derived from the SPIN database; and
3. Measure for range of use (range of use index, RI), considering, e.g., a wide dispersive use, derived from the SPIN database.

The value of each of the three scores should be between 0 and 1. The final exposure index, according to KEMI is calculated as the sum of each sub-score divided by 3 (Dulio et al., 2017).

Although the KEMI index is available in the Norman database, Dr. Stellan Fischer kindly provided the data used within the mapping, which is the most updated dataset available.

The scatter plot displays average P and M scores across different product categories (Figure 5, top) and sectors of use groups (Figure 5, down). The colours represent the Kemi score, which shows the level of emissions for each substance. The size of the bubbles indicates the number of different substances in each group. This chart identifies the level of PM total hazard in SusDat substances grouped by either PC or SU categories.

Following this analysis, certain sectors exhibited higher average scores, indicating their persistence or mobility associated with their emission potential (Kemi score). Notably, these sectors include SU4 (Manufacture of food products) with 227 substances, SU23 (Electricity, steam, gas, water supply and sewage treatment) with 271 substances, and SU 6a (Manufacture of wood and wood products). All the previous sectors of use have elevated average M scores and a significantly high average Kemi score ($\sim 0,7$). Note that, as shown in section 3.1, this figure represents the P and M characteristics of only 4.5% ($n=5453$) of the total number of substances included within the SusDat NORMAN database.

SU 14 (Manufacture of basic metals, including alloys), SU 2a (Mining), and SU 2b (Offshore industries) also ranked among the groups with the highest averaged Kemi and P scores. Their average mobility scores were comparatively among the lowest from another sector of use but were still over the threshold for classifying them as very mobile.

With regard to product categories, aside from PC42 (Electrolytes for batteries) which shows a particularly high average mobility score, it is difficult to distinguish categories with specific profiles. All are characterized by average mobility scores around 0,55 and very similar persistence scores ranging between 0,67 and 0,72.

PM average scores for Product Category groups - Average scenario

PM average scores for Sector of use groups- Average scenario

Figure 5: Scatter plot of the average mobility and persistence score of all substances (average scenario) in a Product Category (top) or Sector of Use (bottom). Colours indicate the Kemi score, a proxy of emission for each substance, while the size of bubbles corresponds to the number of substances considered within each group.

3.5 Conclusion

The main conclusion of this work is that classifying substances based on the robust scenario is challenging due to the very limited availability of experimental data on persistence and mobility. As a result, identifying high-risk sectors based on experimental data is also difficult. Predicted data-based classification (average and conservative scenarios) results show that many substances are classed as very persistent substances and that these are used across all sectors. Unsurprisingly, the upstream chemical sectors (e.g., SU9, SU8, PC19) have the highest number of substances, and as predictive methods often classify most of these as persistent, mobile, and toxic.

The assessment can be refined slightly by analysing the sector of use and product category average scores. Certain sectors and product categories, such as the manufacture of food products, manufacture of wood and wood products, and electrolytes for batteries, stand out for their association with substances showing particularly high average scores. It would be worthwhile to conduct targeted studies on these uses to identify the substances or substance classes involved, to evaluate substitution opportunities.

Nevertheless, the available data primarily highlight the generally high levels of these conservative average scores across all sectors. The absence of quantitative data on uses remains a major barrier to precisely identifying the applications for which substitution efforts should be prioritised.

4 Analysis of substitution challenges based on use data derived from the NORMAN database – Surfactants as a case study

This section presents an alternative approach to determine the sectors and products of use of substances. By analysing the lists in which substances are included within the NORMAN database, it is possible to associate them with certain use categories. The value of this approach lies in significantly broadening the scope of substances under study, from those registered under REACH to the more than 120 000 substances contained in the NORMAN database.

The work presented here aims to assess to what extent, and with what level of confidence, it is possible to identify substances to be prioritised or the safest substitutes.

4.1 Uses data extracted from NORMAN sources lists

The SusDat database⁶ is constructed by aggregating diverse substance lists which group substances according to their chemical classes (such as PFAS), their similar impact (e.g., endocrine-disrupting chemicals, EDCs), or to their applications (e.g. plastic additives).

Labels of the lists were analysed and grouped when they referred to similar uses. Table 17 in Annexes provides the complete list of sources (as of June 2024) and the proposed categorisation of use groups.

Eight types of lists were linked to a particular sector: pharmaceuticals, food-contact materials, children's products, personal care products, plant protection products, biocides, plastic additives, and surfactants.

For this deliverable, it was decided to focus on surfactants and assess the distribution of P and M scores for these substances. We aim to highlight those with the highest PMT potential and investigate if the available data allows to identify potential safer alternatives for them. We specifically chose surfactants over other groups because this category qualified as a technical function group which is considered as a key entry with regards to substitution (for further developments, see Tickner et al., 2015).

Surfactants, the term is based on “surface-active agents”, are chemical compounds that decrease the surface tension between two liquids, a liquid and a gas, or a liquid and a solid. The uses of surfactants are numerous, both in household products and in industrial processes. They are used in large quantities as detergents, but also as emulsifiers, foaming agents, antistatic additives or dispersants.

4.2 Identifying the surfactants of concern

Among the 120 416 substances in the PROMISCES database, 82 160 are in at least one list associated with a use as surfactant.

⁶ <https://www.norman-network.com/nds/susdat/>

The analysis consisted in studying, among these substances, how many are persistent, mobile, and toxic, taking into account that the robustness of the analysis varies depending on whether it is based on experimental data, modelled data, or a lack of data.

4.2.1 Surfactants classified as T according to the robust scenario

As presented in Figure 6, 59 668 of the 82 160 surfactants are classified as Toxic (T) in the robust scenario following the methodology presented in Deliverable D5.1.

Figure 6: Toxic robust classification

The properties of the 59 668 toxic surfactants were then analysed, as presented in Figure 7. Among them, 52 are persistent according to the robust classification, but of these 52 persistent substances none are M according to the robust scenario (i.e. according to experimental data). 2 are mobile according to several predicted results and 3 more are mobile according to 1 model prediction. The 47 remaining are not mobile according to predicted results. These 3+2 should be prioritised for further analysis in terms of substitution.

It is then possible to identify other priority substances using the same type of analysis. With the same level of confidence in the assessment, 403 substances are mobile and toxic according to the robust scenario and persistent according to the average scenario. 404 substances are toxic according to the robust scenario and persistent and mobile according to the average scenario. When the conservative scenario is considered for persistence and mobility, the number of substances identified as potentially PMT becomes very high (N=28 290).

Figure 7: Analysis of the toxic surfactants. This figure must be read as a flow analysis. Among the 59668 substances classified as T, 52 are persistent (Pscore \geq 0.33) according to the robust scenario and 59616 are not (either because Pscore $<$ 0.33 or because no experimental data are available). Among the 52 persistent substances, 0 are mobile (Mscore \geq 0.33) according to the robust scenario, 2 are mobile according to the average of predicted results and 3 more are mobile according to the most conservative predicted results. 47 substances are not mobile according to the most conservative models, and there is no substance for which we do not have data.

4.2.2 Surfactants not classified as T according to the robust scenario

Among the substances not classified as toxic according to the robust scenario, it is still possible to distinguish two cases by taking into account the predicted toxicity data based on the model used by RIVM⁷ (Figure 8).

Most substances not classified as toxic under the robust scenario are not associated with data that would allow for an assessment of their toxicity.

Figure 8: Surfactants not classified as toxic according to the robust scenario

Nevertheless 195 more substances are classified as toxic according to predicted data. Figure 9 below shows the analysis of these compounds. None are both persistent and mobile according to experimental data. But 177 substances are persistent according to the average scenario, including 7+27 that are mobile according to the robust and average scenario respectively.

⁷ <https://rvszoekstelsysteem.rivm.nl/ScreeningTool>

Figure 9: Mapping of surfactants among those classified as toxic according to predicted data.

We then examined, among the 47 substances classified as non-toxic according to RIVM data, whether any were very persistent and very mobile. None are classified as vPvM under the robust scenario. However, 46 of the 47 are considered very persistent under the average scenario. Among them, 3 are also very mobile under the average scenario, while the remaining 43 are considered very mobile under the conservative scenario. Given the uncertainty associated with relying solely on predicted data, these 46 substances could therefore also be regarded as priorities for further investigation into potential substitution.

The final case concerns substances for which no toxicity data are available (Figure 10). The aim is to identify those that are very persistent and very mobile, which would make them a priority for substitution despite the uncertainty regarding their toxicity. A total of 22245 substances were examined. Among these, none are classified as persistent based on experimental data. However, 1503 are considered very persistent under the average scenario, of which 8 are very mobile according to the robust scenario, 10 additional ones under the average scenario, and a further 1242 if the conservative scenario is considered.

Due to time constraints, we did not study the distribution of substances identified as very persistent only under the conservative scenario. Nevertheless, 87% of the substances that the moderate scenario does not identify as persistent in this case are not associated with any data.

Figure 10: Mapping of surfactant for which no data on toxicity is available

4.2.3 Synthesis

Table 1 and Table 2 below summarise the information produced in this study. The approach consists in associating the different results to their “weight of evidence”. We first consider that the weight of evidence is stronger when the assessment is based on experimental data rather than on modelled data. When based on modelled data, it is greater when multiple models are used rather than relying solely on the most conservative one. Therefore, the study enabled an evaluation of the number of surfactants for which substitution should be considered.

The results show that no surfactant can be classified as PMT or vPvM based solely on the experimental data compiled in PROMISCES.

However, 405 substances can be classified as PMT based on robust data for two of the three properties, and on multiple models for the third. These substances should be the focus of more detailed investigation in future work. An additional 8 substances should be specifically studied due to their vPvM status supported by a high weight of evidence.

A similar number of substances (451) may warrant particular attention on the grounds that both persistence and mobility are supported by multiple model outputs.

Finally, among all identified surfactants, at least 37% (N=30 218) may be considered PMT or vPvM based on the results of the most conservative models. This number is high even though many substances lack data for at least one of the three properties.

Table 1: Number of surfactants classified as PMT and weight of evidence

Number of surfactants classified as PMT according to experimental data on the 3 properties		0	0
Number of surfactants classified as PMT according to robust data on 2 properties and 1 modelled data on the third one	Modelled data based on 1 average scenario	405	405
	Modelled data based on 1 conservative scenario	0	
Number of surfactants classified as PMT according to robust data on 1 property and 2 modelled data on the others	Modelled data based on 2 average scenarios	451	28745
	Modelled data based on 1 average scenario and 1 conservative scenario	28102	
	Modelled data based on 2 conservative scenarios	192	
Number of surfactants classified as PMT according to modelled data on the 3 properties	Modelled data based on average scenarios	27	175
	Modelled data based on 1 average scenario and 1 conservative scenario	143	
	Modelled data based on 3 conservative scenarios	5	

Table 2: Number of surfactants classified as non-toxic or without data on toxicity classified as vPvM and weight of evidence

Number of substances classified as vPvM according to robust data		0	0
Number of substances classified as vPvM according to 1 robust and 1 modelled data	Modelled data corresponding to the average scenario	8	8+
	Modelled data corresponding to the conservative scenario	n.d.	
Number of substances classified as vPvM according to 2 modelled data	Both modelled data are based on the average scenario	13	>1298 <3944
	1 modelled data is based on the average scenario, 1 on the conservative scenario	1285	
	Both modelled data correspond to conservative scenarios	< 2646	

4.3 Identifying the safest surfactants

We undertook a similar approach to identify the safest surfactants based on the data compiled in PROMISCES.

In the previous section, it was considered that the substances to prioritise for substitution were those for which we had the most robust evidence demonstrating their hazardous properties. Identifying the safest alternatives requires minimising uncertainty regarding potential hazardous characteristics. In this context, the conservative scenario plays an important role.

Among the 82 160 identified surfactants, 22 491 – 195 = 22 296 substances are not classified as toxic.

Among these, none have experimental data indicating that they are neither mobile nor persistent. In fact, none have experimental data on persistence in general. Only 11 substances have experimental data on mobility.

Based on the conservative scenario, 1 027 substances are classified as non-persistent (substances for which no modelled data are available are, of course, not included). However, none of these have modelling data on mobility. Even when expanding the pool of candidate substances to include those considered non-persistent under the average scenario, the outcome remains the same: none of these have available data on mobility.

A total of 8545 substances are classified as non-toxic and non-mobile under the conservative scenario. However, all of these are considered persistent under both the conservative and average scenarios. Furthermore, under the average scenario, when multiple model results are available, 8529 of the 8545 substances are still classified as persistent.

In conclusion, based on the information compiled within the framework of the PROMISCES project, it is not possible to identify any surfactant for which modelled or experimental data support classification as non-persistent, non-mobile, and non-toxic.

4.4 Conclusion

The work presented in this section represents an original approach aimed at assessing a large number of substances simultaneously and quantifying those that may serve the same technical function:

- i) substances for which substitution should be considered, and
- ii) substances that could be explored as potentially safer alternatives.

Starting from several tens of thousands of substances, it is possible to draw up lists of a few hundred priority substances. However, the study does not allow for the identification of safer alternatives in terms of persistence, mobility, and toxicity.

While the lack of experimental and modelled data inevitably limits the study, this impossibility to identify safe candidates for the substitution of surfactants of concern was unexpected. Further work will be needed to assess the reasons behind this outcome.

5 Substance studies - Benzotriazoles

5.1 Introduction

This section presents a third approach. Certain substances (e.g. Melamine) or substance families have been identified as persistent, mobile, and toxic in different studies (Vetter & Lorenz, 2013; Arp et al., 2023). This is the case for 1H-Benzotriazole, which belongs to a class of compounds with several known commercial or industrial uses.

Ineris has recently worked on Benzotriazoles (Ineris, 2021), and, as part of this work, produced a synthesis covering around ten substances. The research carried out within the PROMISCES project has led to the identification of more than 100 benzotriazoles. It therefore seemed relevant to examine how the results of the PROMISCES project could enrich this initial work, not only for the substances already identified but also for the others, with the aim of addressing large groups of substances. This is why this case study was selected.

5.2 General aspects

5.2.1 Definition and chemical properties

Benzotriazoles are heterocyclic organic compounds belonging to the azole family. Benzotriazoles are synthetic substances and do not occur naturally in the environment.

The first benzotriazole derivative was synthesised at the end of the 19th century. This synthesis remains the same today, with certain improvements made to the reaction conditions:

The basic structure of benzotriazoles is a benzene ring fused to a 5-atom aromatic ring containing two double bonds and 3 nitrogen atoms. Benzotriazole can exist in two tautomeric forms: 1H- and 2H-benzotriazole (left and right respectively). The 1H-tautomer predominates in solution and is the only stable isomer found in the solid state.

1H-benzotriazole is a versatile synthetic intermediate with a unique set of physicochemical properties. Attached to other chemical radicals, 1H-benzotriazole transfers its electronic, steric and stereoelectronic properties to the molecule as a whole (Ineris, 2021).

There are many benzotriazole compounds but those that are produced by industry to a significant extent and have been reported to be present in the environment have the following configurations:

- Benzotriazoles used as corrosion inhibitors have a hydrogen in the 1H- position: these are methyl-, hydroxy- and chloro- derivatives.

- Benzotriazoles used as UV stabilisers generally have a phenol group in the 2H-position. Their molecular weights and structures are more complex. The representative chemical structure of phenolic benzotriazoles is shown below. R1 and R2 represent an ester, a chlorine atom or an additional functional group (e.g. phenol, methyl).

A text search in the Susdat database⁸ combined with a literature review allowed to identify 125 benzotriazole substances. Only those for which tonnage data are available in the ECHA database are presented in Table 3 below.

Table 3: General description of some benzotriazoles (updated from Ineris 2021, data: ECHA, PubChem, OECD (2017), Merck (FDS))

Substance	CAS	Susdat ID	Synonyms
Benzotriazole $C_6H_5N_3$	95-14-7	NS00010261	1H-Benzotriazole; 1,2-Aminozophenylene; 1,2,3 Benzotriazole; 1,2,3-Triazaindene; 1H-benzotriazole; 2H-Benzotriazole
5-methyl-1H-benzotriazole $C_7H_7N_3$	136-85-6	NS00008943	5-methyl-1H-1,2,3-benzotriazole 5-Methylbenzotriazole 5-Methyl-2H-benzotriazole 5-Tolyltriazole 6-methylbenzotriazole
Methyl-1H-Benzotriazole $C_7H_7N_3$	29385-43-1	NS00073843	Tolyltriazole 1H-Benzotriazole, 4(or 5)-methyl- 5-methyl-1H-1,2,3-benzotriazole 1-methyl-1H-benzotriazole 4(ou 5)-Methyl-1H-benzotriazole

⁸ "benzotriazol" was searched in the substance names

Substance	CAS	Susdat ID	Synonyms
1-hydroxybenzotriazole $C_6H_5N_3O$	2592-95-2	NS00007863	1-Hydroxy-1H-benzotriazole Benzazimidol hydrate N-Hydroxybenzotriazole hydrate 1H-Benzotriazole, 1-hydroxy- 1-Hydroxy-1,2,3-benzotirazole 1H-benzotriazol-1-ol
2-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4-(1,1,3,3-tetramethylbutyl)phenol $C_{20}H_{25}N_3O$	3147-75-9	NS00008577	Octrizole; UV-329 2-(benzotriazol-2-yl)-4-(2,4,4-trimethylpentan-2-yl)phenol ; Phenol, 2-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4-(1,1,3,3-tetramethylbutyl)-; 2-(2-Hydroxy-5-t-octylphenyl) benzotriazole ; 2-(2-Hydroxy-5-tert-octylphenyl)benzotriazole ; 2-(2H-1,2,3-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4-(2,4,4-trimethylpentan-2-yl)phenol ; 2-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl) -4-(1,1,3,3-tetramethylbutyl) phenol ; 2-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4-(1,1,3,3-teramethylbutyl)phenol ; 2-(5-tert-octyl-2-hydroxyphenyl)-2H-benzotriazole ; 2-(benzotriazol-2-yl)-4-(2,4,4-trimethylpentan-2-yl)phenol ; UV absorber-1
Bumetrizole $C_{17}H_{18}ClN_3O$	3896-11-5	NS00004466	Bumetrizole; UV-326 2-tert-butyl-6-(5-chlorobenzotriazol-2-yl)-4-methylphenol; 2-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-t-butyl-5'-methylphenyl)-5-chlorobenzotriazole ; 2-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-tert-butyl-5'-methylphenyl)-5-chlorobenzotriazole; 2-(5-Chloro-2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-6-(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-methyl-phenol; Bumetrizolum; 2-tert-Butyl-6-(5-chloro-2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-p-cresol; Phenol, 2-(5-chloro-2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-6-(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-methyl-; UV Absorber-6 ; Tinuvin ; 2-(2'-hydroxy-5'-t-octylphenyl)-benzotriazole ; 2-(3'-tert-butyl-2'hydroxy-5'-methylphenyl)-5-chlorobenzotriazole; 2-(5-Chloro-2-benzotriazolyl)-6-tert-butyl-p-cresol
3-(2H-Benzotriazolyl)-5-(1,1-di-methylethyl)-4-hydroxy-benzenepropanoic acid octyl esters	127519-17-9	NS00114722	UV-384; Tinuvin 384 octyl 3-[3-(benzotriazol-2-yl)-5-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl]propanoate; 3-(2H-Benzotriazolyl)-5-(1,1-di-methylethyl)-4-hydroxy-benzenepropanoic acid octyl esters; 4-methylhexyl 3-[3-(benzotriazol-2-yl)-5-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl] propanoate;

Substance	CAS	Susdat ID	Synonyms
<p>$C_{81}H_{111}N_9O_9$</p>			<p>Benzenepropanoic acid, 3-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-5-(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy-, C7-9-branched and linear alkyl esters;</p> <p>reaction mass of branched and linear C7-C9 alkyl 3-[3-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-5-(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxyphenyl]propionates;</p> <p>Benzenepropanoic acid, 3-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-5-(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy-, C7-9-branched and linear alkyl esters;</p> <p>A mixture of branched and linear C7-C9 alkyl 3-[3-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-5-(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxyphenyl]propionates</p>
<p>2,2'-Methylenebis[6-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4-(1,1,3,3-tetramethylbutyl)phenol]</p> <p>$C_{41}H_{50}N_6O_2$</p>	103597-45-1	NS00004911	<p>Tinuvin 360, UV-360</p> <p>Bisoctrizole</p> <p>2,2'-Methylenebis[4-(1,1,3,3-tetramethylbutyl)-6-benzotriazolylphenol]</p> <p>2,2'-Methylenebis[4-(1,1,3,3-tetramethylbutyl)-6-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)phenol]</p> <p>2,2'-Methylenebis[4-(1,1,3,3-tetramethylbutyl)-6-benzotriazol-2-ylphenol]</p> <p>2,2'-Methylenebis[6-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4-tert-octylphenol]</p>
<p>2-Propenoic acid, 2-methyl-, 2-[3-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4-hydroxyphenyl]ethyl ester</p>	96478-09-0	NS00003213	<p>2-(2-hydroxy-5-(2-(methacryloyloxy)ethyl)phenyl)-2H-benzotriazole</p> <p>Eversorb R03</p> <p>2-[3-(2H-1,2,3-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4-hydroxyphenyl]ethyl 2-methylprop-2-enoate</p>
<p>2-(2H-Benzotriazol-2-yl)-4,6-bis(1-methyl-1-phenylethyl)phenol</p>	70321-86-7	NS00004642	<p>2-(2H-1,2,3-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4,6-bis(2-phenylpropan-2-yl)phenol</p> <p>Phenol, 2-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4,6-bis(1-methyl-1-phenylethyl)-</p> <p>UV-234</p> <p>Eversorb 76</p>

Substance	CAS	Susdat ID	Synonyms
Phenol, 2-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-6-(1-methyl-1-phenylethyl)-4-(1,1,3,3-tetramethylbutyl)- 	73936-91-1	NS00005141	2-(1-Methyl-1-phenylethyl)-4-(1,1,3,3-tetramethylbutyl)-6-(benzotriazol-2-yl)phenol; 2-(2-Hydroxy-3-tert-butyl-5-tert-octylphenyl)-2H-benzotriazol 2-(2H-Benzotriazol-2-yl)-6-(1-methyl-1-phenylethyl)-4-(1,1,3,3-tetramethylbutyl)phenol UV-928 Eversorb 89 Chiguard 5228 CGL 120
2-(2-Hydroxy-3,5-di-tert-pentylphenyl)benzotriazole 	25973-55-1	NS00010624	2-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4,6-ditertpentylphenol 2-(3,5-Di-tert-amyl-2-hydroxyphenyl)benzotriazole 2-(4,7-dihydro-2H-1,2,3-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4,6-bis(2-methylbutan-2-yl)phenol UV-328 Eversorb 74
2-(2H-Benzotriazol-2-yl)-4-methylphenol 	2440-22-4	NS00010695	2-(2'-hydroxy-5'-methylphenyl) benzotriazole 2-(2H-Benzotriazol-2-yl)-p-cresol 2-(2'-Hydroxy-5'-methylphenyl) benzotriazole; 2-(2H-Benzotriazol-2-yl)-4-methylphenol Benazol P Eversorb 71
Benzenepropanoic acid, 3-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-5-(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy-, methyl ester 	84268-33-7	NS00019540	3-[3-tert-butyl-5-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4-hydroxyphenyl]propionate Benzenepropanoic acid, 3-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-5-(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy-, methyl ester methyl 3-[3-(2H-1,2,3-benzotriazol-2-yl)-5-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl]propanoate THASORB UV-1130 BHE

Substance	CAS	Susdat ID	Synonyms
<p>sodium 3-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-5-sec-butyl-4-hydroxybenzenesulfonate</p>	92484-48-5	NS00114722	<p>Benzenesulfonic acid, 3-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4-hydroxy-5-(1-methylpropyl)-, monosodium salt</p> <p>Benzotriazolyl Butylphenol Sulfonate-Na</p> <p>Sodium Benzotriazolyl Butylphenol Sulfonate</p> <p>UV ABSORBER BUK 4499</p>

5.2.2 Regulation

The following paragraphs set out the main legislation in force at the end of 2024 governing the manufacture, uses and emissions of benzotriazoles. This list is not exhaustive.

5.2.3 REACH regulation

Between 2014 and 2024, six benzotriazoles were included on the list of substances of very high concern, candidate for authorisation (SHVC list). They all meet the criteria of Annex XIII for identification as persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic (PBT) or very persistent, very bioaccumulative (vPvB) substances. They are listed in Table 4.

Table 4: Benzotriazoles on the Candidate List

CAS	Name	Year of inclusion
3864-99-1	Phenol, 2-(5-chloro-2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4,6-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-	2015
3896-11-5	Bumetrizole	2024
3846-71-7	2-Benzotriazol-2-yl-4,6-di-tert-butylphenol	2014
3147-75-9	Octrizole	2024
36437-37-3	2-(2H-Benzotriazol-2-yl)-6-(butan-2-yl)-4-tert-butylphenol	2015
25973-55-1	2-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4,6-ditertpentylphenol (UV-328)	2014

Other benzotriazoles are on ECHA's PBT assessment list and/or are currently being assessed. Four of those substances are evaluated with regards to their PMT/vPvM properties. Table 5 lists them.

Table 5: Overview of benzotriazoles on the PBT assessment list or on the CoRAP update for 2025-2027 (Source: ECHA)

CAS	Name	PBT Assessment list	Outcome
70321-86-7	2-(2H-Benzotriazol-2-yl)-4,6-bis(1-methyl-1-phenylethyl)phenol	Under development	PBT
73936-91-1	Phenol, 2-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-6-(1-methyl-1-phenylethyl)-4-(1,1,3,3-tetramethylbutyl)-	Under development	PBT
84268-36-0	Benzenepropanoic acid, 3-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-5-(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy-	Concluded	PBT
95-14-7	1,2,3-Benzotriazole	Concluded	PMT/vPvM
2440-22-4	2-(2H-Benzotriazol-2-yl)-4-methylphenol	Under development	PBT
84268-33-7	Benzenepropanoic acid, 3-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-5-(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy-, methyl ester	Concluded	PBT
29385-43-1	Tolyltriazole	Concluded	PMT/vPvM
92484-48-5	sodium 3-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-5-sec-butyl-4-hydroxybenzenesulfonate	Under development	PMT/vPvM
127519-17-9*	/	Not started	Suspected PMT/vPvM

The substance marked with a * (CAS No. 127519-17-9) is on the CoRAP list for assessment in 2026⁹

5.2.3.1 Sectoral regulations

Among the 124 benzotriazoles identified in this study, 6 are mentioned and authorised in sectoral regulations on cosmetic products¹⁰, detergents¹¹, food contact materials¹², etc. (see Table 6).

As such, no other benzotriazole can be used as a UV filter in cosmetics.

Table 6: Benzotriazoles mentioned in sectoral regulations

CAS	Name	Mentioned in
3864-99-1	Phenol, 2-(5-chloro-2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4,6-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-	List of Authorized Substances: Annex I, Plastics Food Contact Regulation
3896-11-5	Bumetrizole	List of Authorized Substances: Annex I, Plastics Food Contact Regulation
70321-86-7	2-(2H-Benzotriazol-2-yl)-4,6-bis(1-methyl-1-phenylethyl)phenol	List of Authorized Substances: Annex I, Plastics Food Contact Regulation
103597-45-1	Bisocetrizole	Allowed UV Filters: Annex VI, Regulation 1223/2009/EC on Cosmetic Products (< 10%)
2440-22-4	2-(2H-Benzotriazol-2-yl)-4-methylphenol	List of Authorized Substances: Annex I, Plastics Food Contact Regulation
155633-54-8	Drometrizole Trisiloxane	Allowed UV Filters: Annex VI, Regulation 1223/2009/EC on Cosmetic Products (< 15%)

5.2.4 Classification, Labelling, and Packaging

Eight benzotriazoles (listed in Table 7) have an harmonised classification according to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on the classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures (CLP Regulation).

⁹ https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/879660/corap_update_2025-2027_en.pdf/2a2c35da-f341-d0b1-6802-9aab4685e576?t=1742369760682 The Community rolling action plan (CoRAP) lists the substances for which a Member State has provided or will provide an evaluation over the coming years.

¹⁰ Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 November 2009 on cosmetic products

¹¹ Regulation (EC) No 648/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 31 March 2004 on detergents

¹² Commission Regulation (EU) No 10/2011 of 14 January 2011 on plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with food

Table 7: Harmonised classification of benzotriazoles (Source: ECHA¹³)

Substance		Classification		Labelling
Name	CAS	Hazard Class and Category Code(s)	Hazard Statement Code(s)	Pictogram, Signal Word Code(s)
2-(2H-Benzotriazol-2-yl)-5-(octyloxy)phenol	3147-77-1	Aquatic chronic 4	H 413	/
2,2'-Methylenebis[6-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4-(1,1,3,3-tetramethylbutyl)phenol]	103597-45-1	Aquatic chronic 4	H 413	/
4-[[{(1H-Benzotriazol-1-yl)methyl}sulfamoyl]benzoic acid	170292-97-4	Eye Irrit. 2 Aquatic Chronic 2	H319 H411	GHS07 GHS09 Wng
1-hydroxybenzotriazole	2592-95-2	Expl. 1.3	H 203	GHS01 Dgr
1,2,3-Benzotriazole	95-14-7	Aquatic Chronic 2	H411	GHS09
Tolyltriazole	29385-43-1	Aquatic Chronic 2	H411	GHS09
3-(2H-Benzotriazolyl)-5-(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy-benzenepropanoic acid octyl esters	127519-17-9	Aquatic Chronic 2	H411	GHS09
sodium 3-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-5-sec-butyl-4-hydroxybenzenesulfonate	92484-48-5	Eye Dam. 1	H318	GHS05 Dgr

More benzotriazoles have non-harmonised classifications based on declarant's information. Interested readers may refer to Ineris (2021).

¹³ https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/17218/annex_vi_clp_table_atp22_en.xlsx/862452bf-e3dc-324b-73e8-baf076d1d952 (March 2025)

5.3 Synthesis on rationale for substitution of benzotriazoles

Of the 125 benzotriazoles identified, 15 have tonnage data in the ECHA database. They are presented in Table 8. Eight of them have high tonnages, higher than 1 000 tonnes per year, including 3 SVHC substances. In addition, 8 substances are identified on the ECHA's [PBT assessment list](#) or will be assessed for their PBT/vPvB or PMT/vPvM properties.

Using the results of the PROMISCES project, it appears that 13 of the 15 substances have scores higher than 90. One of the substances does not have an assessment, probably due to a mismatch between CAS and SusDat ID.

In more detail:

- Persistence: 12 of the 15 substances are classified as very persistent (vP) according to the conservative scenario, which means that they were classified as such by at least one model. 1 is classified as non-persistent (nP) which means that all there are model results for it but no model classifies it as persistent. 2 do not have a classification for persistence due to a lack of modelled data.
- Mobility: 5 of the substances are mobile or very mobile (M/vM) according to the conservative scenario, and 7 are classified as non-mobile (nM).
- Toxicity: 14 of the 15 substances are classified as toxic (T) according to the conservative scenario, and these results are broadly confirmed by the robust scenario, which assesses 13 of these 14 substances as toxic.

It should be noted that in most cases only one (or no) model result is available to assess the mobility. Furthermore, average classifications concerning the persistence are never contradictory with the conservative classifications; it means that when several models are available to assess the persistence, the average result is the same as the conservative one¹⁴. Consequently, the average scenario does not bring further information than the robust scenario. This is why classification from the average scenario are not presented in Table 8. In addition, none of these substances has experimental data to assess mobility and persistence. This is why the robust scenario only provides information on toxicity.

The Swedish Chemicals Agency (KEMI) developed a tool, the PRIO tool, that helps find substances that are hazardous for human health and the environment by screening different regulatory lists. This tool was used to check if other Benzotriazoles are already identified as candidates for substitution in European regulations. Of the 110 substances with no tonnage data, the PRIO tool¹⁵ identifies 5 as priorities for substitution, 3 of which being SVHCs and 2

¹⁴ It should be noted that the definition of the average scenario used here is not exactly the same as in other works within the PROMISCES project. In some cases, the average scenario is only calculated when at least two modeled data points are available. Here, we consider that when only one data point is available, the conservative scenario corresponds to the average scenario. The average scenario is said to contradict the conservative scenario when the average of two (or more) predicted data lead to a different classification from the conservative one.

¹⁵ <https://www.kemi.se/prioguiden/english/start>

being hazardous for the environment with long-term effects (see Table 10). The absence of results for the other 105 substances may mean (i) either that the substance's properties do not meet any of the criteria in PRIO¹⁶, or (ii) that the substance is not included in the references that PRIO refers to. This second situation may be linked to substances for which few or no data are available and that may still fall under PRIO's criteria. Among the 125 substances, 15 have no experimental or modelled data on persistence, mobility and toxicity.

Using PROMISCES' results, the conservative classification of those substances was analysed, and results are presented in Table 9.

The general conclusion is as follows: in the absence of experimental data, the use of modelled data leads to the identification of benzotriazoles as a family whose substitution should be seriously considered. 80 of the 125 substances show at least 2 of the hazardous properties considered in this report (persistence, mobility and toxicity¹⁷): 12 of 15 among the substances with tonnage data, and 68 of 110 among the others. Furthermore 43 substances¹⁸ are classified (at least) as PMT or vPvM according to the conservative/average scenario¹⁹.

¹⁶ Criteria for phase-out substances and priority risk-reduction substances are precisely explained here : <https://www.kemi.se/prioguiden/english/start/prio-criteria-for-phase-out-substances-and-priority-risk-reduction-substances>

¹⁷ This kind of approach is for instance used in the Biocide product regulation. According to Article 10 of Regulation (EU) No 528/2012, the substitution of an active substance may be considered if it meets two of the [three] criteria to be considered for classification as a PBT (see Annex XIII of REACH)

¹⁸ 5 among the 15 with tonnage data, 38 among the others. And mobility properties could not be assessed for 11 substances (8 vPT + 3 PT).

Table 8: Overview of benzotriazoles with tonnage data and rationales for substitution

Substance ID			REACH information				PROMISCES results		
SusdatID	CAS No.	Name (shortened)	Tonnage band (t)	#PC ⁽¹⁾	#SU ⁽²⁾	SVHC	PBT Assessment list/CoRAP	Conservative classification	Robust classification
NS00010261	95-14-7	1,2,3-Benzotriazole	1000-10000	12	6	No	PMT/vPvM	vPvMT	0
NS00008577	3147-75-9	Octrizole	1000-10000	15	2	Yes (vPvB)	PBT	vPMT	T
NS00004466	3896-11-5	Bumetrizole	1000-10000	19	6	Yes (vPvB)	PBT	vPnMT	T
NS00004642	70321-86-7	2-(2H-Benzotriazol-2-yl)...	1000-10000	3	5	No	PBT	vPnMT	T
NS00005141	73936-91-1	Phenol, 2-(2H-benzotriaz...	1000-10000	4	3	No	PBT	vPnMT	T
NS00010695	2440-22-4	2-(2H-Benzotriazol-2-yl)...	1000-10000	3	7	No	PBT	vPnMT	T
NS00073843	29385-43-1	Tolyltriazole	1000-10000	14	4	No	PMT/vPvM	T	T
NS00004911	103597-45-1	Bisoctrizole	100-	2	3	No	-	vPnMT	T
NS00010624	25973-55-1	2-(2-Hydroxy-3,5-di-tert-...	100-1000	16	6	Yes (PBT/vPvB)	PBT/vPvB	vPnMT	T
NS00076107	127519-17-9	A mixture of branched...	100-	0	0	No	Suspected PMT/vPvM ⁽³⁾	0	0
NS00007863	2592-95-2	1-Hydroxybenzotriazole	10-100	5	4	No	-	vPvMT	T
NS00114722	92484-48-5	sodium 3-(2H-ben...	10-	0	0	No	PMT/vPvM	nPT	T
NS00019540	84268-33-7	Benzenepropanoic...	1-10	1	1	No	PBT	vPMT	T
NS00008943	136-85-6	5-Methyl-1H-benzo...	1-10	2	2	No	-	vPvMT	0
NS00003213	96478-09-0	2-Propenoic acid...	1-	1	0	No	-	vPnMT	T

⁽¹⁾Number of product categories associated with the substance in the ECHA data

⁽²⁾Number of sectors of use associated with the substance in the ECHA data

⁽³⁾Exposure of environment and Wide dispersive use are also mentioned as rationale for inclusion on the CORaP list

Table 9: Overview of the remaining benzotriazoles, PROMISCES results, use data in REACH and results from the PRIO tool

Conservative classification in PROMISCES	Number of benzotriazoles	Number of benzotriazoles classified as T in the Robust classification	Including substances with PC/SU data in REACH	Number of benzotriazoles identified in the PRIO tool
vPvMT	25	25	1	0
vPMT	13	13	1	0
vPnMT	19	19	1	5
vPT	8	8	0	0
PT	3	3	0	0
vPnM	1	0	0	0
T	16	16	0	0
nPT	10	10	0	0
0	15	0	0	0
Total	110	94	3	5

Table 10: Results from the PRIO tool for the 5 benzotriazoles without tonnage data, identified in the tool

CAS No.	Priority level	Criteria
3864-99-1	Phase-out substance	PBT/vPvB
3147-77-1	Priority risk-reduction substance	Environmentally hazardous long-term effects
3846-71-7	Phase-out substance	PBT/vPvB
36437-37-3	Phase-out substance	PBT/vPvB
125304-04-3	Priority risk-reduction substance	Environmentally hazardous long-term effects

5.4 Production and uses

5.4.1 General economic data

Benzotriazoles are chemical compounds produced globally, with most of the production coming from Asia. They have a wide range of applications and are used in many industrial sectors (see below). These compounds have been manufactured and marketed in the United States since the late 1950s. However, obtaining recent market data is challenging.

Several benzotriazoles are produced in volumes exceeding 500 tonnes per year (Cantwell et al., 2015), which aligns with the tonnage data available in the ECHA database. The consumption of benzotriazoles in plastics in North America increased from 2000 tonnes in the late 1990s to 2500 tonnes in 2001 (Crawford, 1999). In total, over 9000 tonnes of benzotriazoles are estimated to be used annually in the United States (Chung et al., 2018).

The use of benzotriazole (CAS No. 95-14-7) in formulations has been increasing since the 2000s in Sweden, Norway, and Denmark²⁰ (Substance in Preparations in Nordic Countries, 2021).

According to Global Market Insights²¹, In 2023, the global benzotriazole market was valued at approximately \$390 million and is projected to grow at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of over 8.6% from 2024 to 2032. The Asia-Pacific region, particularly China, holds a significant position in this industry, with a market size of \$157.2 million in 2023, expected to surpass \$319.8 million by 2032. This growth is driven by increasing demand for corrosion inhibitors and UV stabilizers across sectors such as automotive, electronics, and construction (see below). However, Global Market Insights also mentions that the market may face challenges due to regulatory constraints and environmental concerns. The necessity to invest in safe and sustainable production of benzotriazoles or alternatives is specifically mentioned.

According to the data on benzotriazoles registered under the REACH Regulation (see Table 8), benzotriazoles are manufactured in and / or imported to the European Economic Area, at ≥ 7323 to < 73230 tonnes per year.

²⁰ Substance in Preparations in Nordic Countries. BENZOTRIAZOL. Retrieved from the Spin database (<https://www.spin2000.net/>) <http://spin2000.net/spinmy-graphics/?Report=SPINuseTotal&Casnr=95147&command=Render> (accessed in October 2024)

²¹ <https://www.gminsights.com/fr/industry-analysis/benzotriazole-market>

5.4.2 Uses

Benzotriazoles serve two main functions: absorbing UV radiation and inhibiting corrosion in the materials and products in which they are incorporated.

5.4.3 UV absorbers

UV absorbers prevent the degradation of the products in which they are used by converting UV radiation into harmless thermal energy. Benzotriazoles UV absorbers (BUV) are generally added in low concentrations: 0.1-0.5% of product weight (Danish Ministry of Environment and Food & The Danish Environmental Protection Agency, 2015; Crawford, 1999).

Benzotriazole derivatives such as UV-326, -327, -328, -329, -360, -P, contain a phenol group that can absorb the full spectrum of UV light: UV-A (320-400 nm) and UV-B (280-320 nm) (Montesdeoca-Esponda et al., 2021).

According to information collected by Germany and presented in the Annex XV report of the proposal for identification of 2-(2h-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4-(tert-butyl)-6-(sec-butyl)phenol (uv-350, CAS No. 36437-37-3) as a substance of very high concern, approximately 50% of BUV are used in paints, 40% in plastics, rubbers and polyurethanes and 10% in cosmetics (Germany, 2015).

The various uses of benzotriazoles as UV absorbers are listed in the following paragraphs.

Table 11 provides a non-exhaustive list of benzotriazoles known to be used as UV absorbers in the following sectors.

Construction materials

BUV are used in the construction sector to protect materials from discolouration, brittleness, loss of gloss and chemical degradation. Among other applications, BUV are mainly used in:

- Coatings in architectural coatings (e.g., for walls, façades), industrial coatings (e.g., for surfaces exposed to high temperatures, UV radiation, or harsh weather) or paints used on wood, metals, or plastics
- Sealants, especially in polymer-based materials used outdoors
- Adhesives designed for outdoor use or exposure to UV radiation
- Plastic films used in construction like UV-protective films for windows, greenhouses, or temporary roofing materials
- Polymers to produce fibres, construction membranes and insulation for buildings, profiles for windows, doors, terraces and fences, pipes and fittings and road signs (SpecialChem, 2025).

Transport

BUV (Hydroxyphenylbenzotriazoles, i.e. benzotriazoles containing 2(2-hydroxyphenyl)2H-benzotriazole) in their formula, such as UV-234, -328, -384, -928 and -1130) are widely used in the transport sector to prevent discolouration of surfaces (paints, plastics used externally and internally), loss of gloss, cracking or hardening of plastics and elastomers and premature ageing of materials exposed to light and heat. Typical applications include:

- Exterior coatings like paints and varnishes on cars, aeroplanes, trains, and boats, or transparent or coloured coatings on metal or plastic surfaces
- Plastics and Composite Materials on dashboards, door panels, centre consoles; bumpers, headlamp housings, exterior mirrors; or more generally plastic components exposed to light inside aircraft or train cabins
- UV-protective films for tinted windows or technical glazing, or films used for panoramic roofs or sunroofs in vehicles
- Sealants used for instance in window seals and other exposed joints
- Adhesives used for instance in car body assembly or interior fittings (Danish Ministry of Environment and Food & The Danish Environmental Protection Agency, 2015; Crawford, 1999)

Plastic and rubber

In addition to applications in construction and transport, BUVs are used in various polymers to produce plastics. Many plastic articles are intended for outdoor use and are therefore highly exposed to UV. BUVs are therefore widely included in these products. They are also present in indoor products (toys, packaging, electronics, etc.) to prevent their yellowing

They are commonly used in many polymers: polyesters, polyacetals, styrenes, polycarbonates, polyolefins, polyamides, polyalkylenes and PVC (Danish Ministry of Environment and Food & The Danish Environmental Protection Agency, 2015).

Cosmetic products

Benzotriazoles are mainly used in cosmetics as UV absorbers to protect both the product and the skin from ultraviolet radiation, stabilise light-sensitive ingredients, and extend the shelf life of formulations. As mentioned in section 5.2.3.1, only two benzotriazoles (CAS No. 103597-45-1 and CAS No. 155633-54-8) are authorised in Europe as UV filters in cosmetics.

Others

UV absorbers are also used in other applications, particularly in the textile industry, to enhance product resistance and durability. Some studies have specifically identified the presence of benzotriazoles in clothing prints and in elastane, which is used for example in the manufacture of socks (Liu et al., 2017).

Table 11: Non-exhaustive inventory of benzotriazoles used as UV absorbers in different sectors

CAS No.	Name or Synonym ^(a)	Construction	Transport	Cosmetics	Other	Source
3896-11-5	UV-326	x	x	x	x	(Danish Ministry of Environment and Food & The Danish Environmental Protection Agency, 2015; Inci Beauty, 2025; Montesdeoca-Esponda et al., 2013; ECHA, 2025)
103597-45-1	UV-360	x	x	x		(Danish Ministry of Environment and Food & The Danish Environmental Protection Agency, 2015; Inci Beauty, 2025; ECHA, 2025)
125304-04-3	UV-571	x	x	x		(Danish Ministry of Environment and Food & The Danish Environmental Protection Agency, 2015; Inci Beauty, 2025; BV MPI Chemie, 2025)
127519-17-9	UV-384	x	x			(Danish Ministry of Environment and Food & The Danish Environmental Protection Agency, 2015; ECHA, 2025)
136-85-6	5-Methyl-1H-benzotriazole	x				(Chung et al., 2018)
155633-54-8	Drometrizole Trisiloxane			x		(Danish Ministry of Environment and Food & The Danish Environmental Protection Agency, 2015; National Center for Biotechnology Information, 2025)
2440-22-4	UV-P	x	x		x	(Danish Ministry of Environment and Food & The Danish Environmental Protection Agency, 2015; ECHA, 2025)
25973-55-1	UV-328	x	x			(Danish Ministry of Environment and Food & The Danish Environmental Protection Agency, 2015; ECHA, 2025; Germany, 2014)
29385-43-1	Tolyltriazole	x				(ECHA, 2025)
3147-75-9	UV-329	x	x		x	(Danish Ministry of Environment and Food & The Danish Environmental Protection Agency, 2015; ECHA, 2025)
3147-76-0	UV-PS	x				(ECHA, 2025)
36437-37-3	UV-350	x	x			(Germany, 2015)
3846-71-7	UV-320		x			(Danish Ministry of Environment and Food & The Danish Environmental Protection Agency, 2015)
3864-99-1	UV-327	x	x			(Danish Ministry of Environment and Food & The Danish Environmental Protection Agency, 2015)
70321-86-7	UV-234	x	x		x	(Danish Ministry of Environment and Food & The Danish Environmental Protection Agency, 2015; BV MPI Chemie, 2025; ECHA, 2025)
73936-91-1	UV-928	x	x			(Danish Ministry of Environment and Food & The Danish Environmental Protection Agency, 2015; ECHA, 2025)
84268-33-7	UV-1130	x				(Danish Ministry of Environment and Food & The Danish Environmental Protection Agency, 2015)
95-14-7	1,2,3-Benzotriazole	x	x		x	(Chung et al. 2018; ECHA, 2025)

^(a)For the sake of simplicity, when available, the name of the substance used as a UV absorber is preferred over the chemical name.

5.4.4 Corrosion inhibitors

Benzotriazoles are commonly used as corrosion inhibitors in many industrial processes and in household products.

Substances like 1H-benzotriazole and tolyltriazole form a thin complex on metal surfaces like copper-based alloys, steel, cadmium and nickel that protects the underlying metal from corrosion over long periods. (Weiss et al., 2006; Parook et al. 2015).

Some uses of benzotriazoles as corrosion inhibitors are listed in the following paragraphs. Table 12 provides a non-exhaustive list of benzotriazoles used in those sectors.

Mechanical applications

Benzotriazoles are commonly used as corrosion inhibitors in mechanical applications, particularly for the protection of metal parts exposed to harsh conditions such as humidity, high temperatures, or technical fluids. Their specific affinity for copper and its alloys (such as brass and bronze) makes them valuable additives in a range of mechanical systems to preserve the integrity of metal components, reduce corrosion-related wear, and extend the lifespan of equipment. Typical applications include:

- Coolants and cutting fluids: In metalworking processes, cutting fluids may contain benzotriazoles to protect copper-based components and internal metallic circuits from corrosion.
- Lubricants and engine oils: Benzotriazoles are added to industrial oils and greases to prevent surface degradation of critical metal components like bearings, gears, and pistons, by forming a protective passivation layer.
- Braking and steering systems: They are sometimes found in technical fluids used in hydraulic or brake systems, especially when copper or copper alloy components are present.
- Closed-loop cooling systems (e.g. in combustion engines): These substances are included in antifreeze or coolant formulations (at concentrations of up to 10%) to prolong the lifespan of metallic parts.
- The combination of corrosion-inhibiting and UV-absorbing properties makes benzotriazoles valuable additives in paints and coatings used in the mechanical sector

Household cleaning

Benzotriazoles are used in certain cleaning products, for their anticorrosive properties.

- Metal surface cleaners: Benzotriazoles are included in formulations designed to protect metal surfaces (such as copper, brass, or aluminium) from corrosion during or after cleaning. They also protect silver products and act as a polishing agent (Janna et al., 2011).
- Dishwasher and laundry products: Benzotriazoles are found in some dishwasher tablets and industrial laundry detergents to prevent corrosion of metal components inside machines (such as heating elements and pipes). In Germany, 80 tonnes of benzotriazoles were for instance used in dishwashers in 2010 (Vetter & Lorenz, 2013).
- Automotive cleaning products: Benzotriazoles can be present in products used in garages for the interior and exterior cleaning of vehicles, particularly those designed

to clean or protect exposed metal parts. and cleaners for mechanical parts used in garages or workshops.

Other uses

Benzotriazoles are also used in inks to protect the metal parts of printers and photocopiers (Shi et al., 2019).

Table 12: Non-exhaustive inventory of benzotriazoles used as corrosion inhibitors in different sectors

CAS No.	Name	Mechanics	Cleaning	Source
136-85-6	5-methyl-1H-benzotriazole	x	x	(Janna et al., 2011; Shi et al., 2019)
2592-95-2	1-hydroxybenzotriazole		x	(ECHA, 2025)
25973-55-1	2-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4,6-ditertpentylphenol		x	(ECHA, 2025)
29385-43-1	Methyl-1H-Benzotriazole	x	x	(ECHA, 2025; Hart et al., 2004)
29878-31-7	4-methyl-1H-benzotriazole	x	x	(Janna et al., 2011; Shi et al., 2019)
3147-75-9	2-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4-(1,1,3,3-tetramethylbutyl)phenol		x	(ECHA, 2025)
4184-79-6	5,6-dimethyl-1H-benzotriazole	x	x	(Janna et al., 2011; Shi et al., 2019)
94-97-3	5-chlorobenzotriazole	x	x	(Janna et al., 2011; Shi et al., 2019)
95-14-7	Benzotriazole	x	x	(ECHA, 2025; Hart et al., 2004; Janna et al., 2011; Shi et al., 2019)
3896-11-5	Bumetrizole		x	(ECHA, 2025)

5.4.5 Other uses

Benzotriazoles are widely used in organic synthesis and pharmaceutical chemistry. They are important intermediates for the synthesis of organic products such as β -amido ketones, aldehydes, β -ketoesters, which are themselves used as intermediates to produce numerous bioactive molecules.

They can also be used as reagents for acylation and thioacylation reactions, and act as ionic liquids (Pereira et al., 2007).

Lastly, they can act as protective groups, making it possible during reactions to deliberately block the reactivity of functional groups in a molecule (Muvvala et al., 2013).

Derivatives of 1,2,3-benzotriazole are the subject of much research in the pharmaceutical industry as they have many applications in particular thanks to their biological activities as analgesic, antifungal, antibacterial, antiparasitic, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, anti-seizure, and protein kinase inhibitor (Muvvala S. Sudhir et al., 2013).

The benzotriazole functional group has been frequently used to develop innovative drugs, particularly in the fight against cancer. Vorozole is a benzotriazole derivative that has been clinically tested as an anti-cancer agent. 4,5,6,7-tetrabromobenzotriazole, meanwhile, is a commercially available cancer treatment compound (Yu Ren, 201

5.5 Alternatives

As detailed in Section 5.3, a number of benzotriazoles exhibit hazardous properties to human health and/or the environment. Furthermore, although not addressed extensively in this report, the presence of benzotriazoles has been documented in multiple environmental compartments, including ambient air, surface waters, sediments, soils, and biota (Ineris, 2021). These substances demonstrate a high resistance to degradation processes and are notably persistent in aquatic environments. Current evidence indicates that conventional wastewater treatment technologies achieve only limited removal of benzotriazoles, and the development of more effective treatment solutions remains a significant technical challenge. These considerations, both individually and collectively, underscore the need to explore preventive approaches to benzotriazole pollution and to evaluate opportunities for their substitution (Chung et al., 2018; Ineris, 2021).

5.5.1 Alternatives as UV absorbers in construction, transport, plastics and rubbers

In this section, the identification of possible substitutes for benzotriazoles was carried out based on a large literature review, initiated in previous work by Ineris (2021) and updated.

In construction materials, transports and many applications in plastics and rubbers, the alternatives must exhibit long-term stability, withstand weathering, and have low migration potential. Benzotriazoles absorb between 390 and 280 nm and offer good colour stability. Potential alternatives to benzotriazoles in coatings, polymers, adhesive and sealants include:

- Triazines (e.g., Cyasorb UV-1577 and Tinuvin 400): they are high-performance UV absorbers with thermal stability, particularly suited for engineering plastics and architectural coatings (SpecialChem, 2025).
- Hindered Amine Light Stabilizers (HALS): they are not UV absorbers²² but are particularly effective and have already been used as an additive in silane-modified polymer seals. Their performance compared with benzotriazoles is widely recognised. These alternative seals can be used in applications requiring high performance, for example in the automotive industry coatings or outdoor polymer applications (Germany, 2015; Omya, 2020).
- Benzophenones such as 2,2'-Dihydroxy-4-methoxybenzophenone. Although structurally similar to benzotriazoles, some are considered safer and remain in use in construction applications. They offer moderate absorption between 390 and 230 nm and can be subjected to high temperatures (Ineris, 2021).
- Oxalic anilides are more recent UV absorbers showing low volatility and excellent UV resistance for high-end coatings. They absorb between 320 and 280nm and are suitable for high-temperature processing (Ineris, 2021; SpecialChem, 2025).
- Benzylidene malonates, particularly for industrial coatings (SpecialChem, 2025).

²² They act by inhibiting propagation by donating protons during photodegradation rather than initiating it (Germany, 2015).

- Formamidine, which offers a wide absorption range (SpecialChem, 2025).
- Some cyanoacrylates (e.g. Uvinul 3039 and Uvinul 3030) are used as UV absorber. suitable for light stability of a variety of polymers, like PVC, PUR, polyesters and PET.

In order to compare the different alternatives based on the work carried out in the PROMISCES project, a comprehensive inventory of these substances was compiled. The SpecialChem²³ website was particularly useful as it references a very large number of products available on the market and allows searching by classes of compounds. For most of the classes, the entire inventory of products was compiled, but for benzotriazoles and HALS, the catalogue is too large to perform this task without automated queries (e.g., 613 products where the chemical substance belongs to the HALS class are listed as UV stabilizers). In this case, we examined the composition of the catalogue products in the order in which they appeared (see link in the Table below). The search was stopped when 10 substances corresponding to 10 different CAS numbers were identified. Approximately 300 products were analysed to identify those 10 different substances.

Table 13 provides an overview of the number of products sold as UV stabilizers for polymers, coatings, adhesives or sealants as referenced on the SpecialChem website according to the chemical class of the substances used. The number of different substances further analysed in this report is also presented. For benzotriazoles and HALS the inventory is probably not exhaustive.

Table 13: Number of products (and corresponding substances with their chemical classes) identified as UV stabilizers

Chemical class	Number of products ^(a)	Number of different CAS No.	Source
Benzotriazoles	311	15	Link
Triazines	83	9	Link
HALS	613	10	Link
Benzophenones	19	8	Link
Benzylidene malonates	/	1	Link
Formamidine	/	2	Link , Link
Cyanocrilates	13	3	Link
Oxalic anilides	5	2	Link

(a)Number of products listed on specialchem.com for each chemical class. Classes without numbers were identified on producers' websites.

Table 14 presents an analysis of the hazards of identified potential alternatives based on the data collected during the project and the selected criteria.

In the absence of experimental data on persistence and mobility that would allow classification according to the "robust" scenario as outlined in deliverable D5.1, the table presents modelled results

²³ <https://www.specialchem.com/>

based on the "average" scenario. Conversely, for toxicity, the classification according to the robust scenario is the one for which the most information is available.

Table 14: Analysis of alternatives of UV absorbers according to PROMISCES results

CAS No.	Susdat ID	P score ^(a)	P class ^(b)	M score ^(a)	M class ^(b)	T class ^(c)
Benzotriazoles						
729335	NS00004466	0,82	vP	0,31	nM	T
70321-86-7	NS00004642	0,85	vP	0,12	nM	T
3147-75-9	NS00008577	0,85	vP	0,35	M	T
103597-45-1	NS00004911	0,83	vP	0,12	nM	T
25973-55-1	NS00010624	0,85	vP	0,17	nM	T
125304-04-3	NS00113144	n.d.	-	n.d.	-	0
3846-71-7	NS00005766	0,85	vP	0,32	nM	T
2440-22-4	NS00010695	0,82	vP	0,31	nM	T
3864-99-1	NS00002300	0,85	vP	0,19	nM	T
127519-17-9	NS00076107	n.d.	-	n.d.	-	0
3147-76-0	NS00015577	0,82	vP	0,27	nM	T
36437-37-3	NS00009103	0,85	vP	0,33	M	T
73936-91-1	NS00005141	0,85	vP	0,12	nM	T
84268-33-7	NS00019540	0,83	vP	0,40	M	T
Triazines						
2725-22-6	NS00020178	0,83	vP	0,10	nM	T
147315-50-2	NS00009561	0,83	vP	0,12	nM	T
137658-79-8	NS00003154	0,83	vP	0,10	nM	T
82451-48-7*	NS00112572	n.d.	-	n.d.	-	0
193098-40-7	NS00113136	n.d.	-	n.d.	-	0
71878-19-8*	NS00112573	n.d.	-	n.d.	-	0
106990-43-6*	NS00002443	0,77	vP	n.d.	-	T
HALS						
192268-64-7	NS00112486	n.d.	-	n.d.	-	0
65447-77-0	NS00008636	0,21	nP	n.d.	-	T
52829-07-9	NS00014950	0,60	vP	0,14	nM	T
136504-96-6	NS00074345	n.d.	-	n.d.	-	0
41556-26-7	NS00008249	0,60	vP	0,11	nM	T
167078-06-0	NS00112485	n.d.	-	n.d.	-	0
70624-18-9	NS00112574	n.d.	-	n.d.	-	0
91788-83-9	NS00112627	0,612	vP	0,15	nM	T
68548-08-3	NS00015575	0,622	vP	0,44	M	T
Benzophenones						

CAS No.	Susdat ID	P score ^(a)	P class ^(b)	M score ^(a)	M class ^(b)	T class ^(c)
117-99-7	NS00006163	0,81	vP	0,40	M	T
131-57-7	NS00000222	0,82	vP	0,39	M	T
1843-05-6	NS00005821	0,84	vP	0,18	nM	T
131-56-6	NS00001568	0,82	vP	0,39	M	T
131-55-5	NS00002972	0,62	vP	0,38	M	T
131-54-4	NS00008303	0,82	vP	0,38	M	T
131-53-3	NS00005730	0,82	vP	0,40	M	T
119-61-9	NS00010632	0,62	vP	0,39	M	T
Formamidine						
57834-33-0	NS00019908	0,81949	vP	0,31	nM	T
Cyanoacrylates						
178671-58-4	NS00003527	0,82	vP	0,10	nM	T
5232-99-5	NS00002771	0,82	vP	0,36	M	T
6197-30-4	NS00010308	0,85	vP	0,14	nM	T
Oxalic anilides						
23949-66-8	NS00009918	0,63	vP	0,28	nM	T
82493-14-9	NS00128160	n.d.	-	n.d.	-	0
Benzylidene malonates						
7443-25-6	NS00006878	0,65750	vP	0,49	M	T

Note: (a) P Score and M Score correspond to the average scenario, as presented in D5.1; (b) P Class. and M Class. correspond to the classification according to the average scenario, as presented in D5.1; (c) T class. corresponds to the robust scenario.

The first outcome of this analysis is the observation of a high degree of similarity in the hazard properties of the identified alternatives. All substances for which modelled persistence data are available, except one (CAS 65447-77-0, from the HALS class), have scores greater than 0,5 and are therefore classified as very persistent (vP). However, if the actual score is considered instead of the binary classification, HALS appear to be less persistent than the other substance classes studied. This non-binary approach may be justified in the context of more refined multicriteria analyses, especially if one seeks to account for the fact that the environmental implications differ between substances with half-lives of several dozen days and those with half-lives of several years. Nevertheless, this is not the approach currently adopted in the regulatory framework.

Benzophenones emerge as the least suitable class of compounds, with all substances being classified as toxic and all but one as mobile. Their global scores are also the highest. In this respect, they do not appear to be a viable option for substituting benzotriazoles, which generally exhibit similar characteristics.

HALS substances for which data are available also appear to be less mobile overall. It remains difficult to draw conclusions for the other classes due to the limited number of substances identified.

5.5.2 Alternatives as UV filters in cosmetic products

UV filters are defined in Cosmetic Regulation (EC) n° 1223/2009 as “substances which are exclusively or mainly intended to protect the skin against certain UV radiation by absorbing, reflecting, or scattering UV radiation”. Annex VI of this regulation mentions the list of approved UV filters for cosmetic use, with a total of 33 references corresponding to 29 compounds and 35 CAS numbers²⁴. 2 compounds are inorganics (zinc oxide and titanium oxide) and 27 are organic UV filters. Some can be present in non-nano or nano forms.

Alternatives to benzotriazoles for UV filtration in cosmetics include different chemical classes like salicylates (ethylhexyl salicylate, homosalate...), which are inexpensive but less effective compared to other filters and filtering only UV-B rays. Cinnamates (octocrylene...) are highly effective at filtering UV-B rays but, for some of them, have low photostability. Benzophenones which can absorb both UV-A and UV-B rays, present relatively low effectiveness, but help increase the sun protection factor when combined with other filters.

Some of these alternatives may exhibit hazardous properties that warrant their own substitution. For example, octocrylene is currently under evaluation for its PBT properties and is toxic to the aquatic environment (ECHA, 2025).

In Table 15 below, the alternatives listed in Annex VI of the Cosmetic Regulation are compared based on the results obtained from the PROMISCES project. The work of Jesus et al. (2022) shows that the following substances are the most frequently used in sunscreens available on the market in 2021: avobenzene (BMDDBM, CAS No. 70356-09-1), octocrylene (OC, CAS No. 6197-30-4), and bis-ethylhexyloxyphenol methoxyphenyl triazine (Tinosorb S, CAS No. 187393-00-6). Their usage frequencies were in 2021 between approximately 45% and 75%. DTS (CAS No. 155633-54-8) and Tinosorb M (CAS No. 103597-45-1) are the two authorized benzotriazoles. Their use declined between 2015 and 2021, with usage frequency dropping from around 20% to 15% and 10% respectively, “probably related to human and environmental safety issues” as stated in Jesus et al. (2022).

In the absence of experimental data on persistence and mobility that would allow classification according to the "robust" scenario as outlined in deliverable D5.1, the table presents modelled results based on the "average" scenario. Conversely, for toxicity, the classification according to the robust scenario is the one for which the most information is available. The "Global score" is also indicated.

The results lead to an unexpected result. Excluding the 5 substances for which no data are available (4 of which are actually used in sunscreens, and 1 that appears to be either not used or used only marginally), all substances but one are classified as very persistent. Only Iscotrizinol (CAS No. 154702-15-5) is classified as non-persistent; however, it is toxic. Seven substances are classified as mobile, and nine substances, including the two benzotriazoles, are classified as non-mobile. Among the

²⁴ For instance, in Annex VI, Ref No 6 corresponds to 4 different salts of 2-Phenylbenzimidazole-5-sulfonic acid and 4 CAS numbers.

substances for which data allow classification for persistence, mobility, and toxicity, the safest substance appears to be DTS (CAS No. 155633-54-8), which is a benzotriazole.

This assessment of substitution possibilities for benzotriazoles in cosmetics remains partial. It should, for instance, be supplemented with techno-economic information to objectively assess performance and, in the context of the “Safe and Sustainable by Design” concept, evaluate risks. This would require accounting for exposure, hence concentration levels, and, as a result, complex situations such as substance synergies that may allow for reduced concentrations. It should also consider the study of new substances that are not yet authorized and still in the cosmetic industry R&D pipeline, but could be subject to future authorization requests. Such work falls beyond the scope of the present study.

The aim here was to assess to what extent the data consolidated within the PROMISCES project, along with the indicators developed, would allow a diagnosis to be made regarding the safest substances to use. The first conclusion is that the lack of experimental or modelled data prevents a fully comprehensive assessment. The second is that no candidates for substitution were identified in the context of this investigation (within the limitations previously outlined).

Table 15: Analysis of alternatives of UV filters according to PROMISCES results

	Susdat ID	Cas No.	Name	Name in Jesus et al., 2022	P score ^(a)	P class ^(b)	M score ^(a)	M class ^(b)	T class ^(c)	Global score
UV filters identified ^(d) in Jesus et al., 2022	NS00002639	70356-09-1	Butyl methoxy...	BMDBM	0,82	vP	0,37	M	T	153,5
	NS00010308	6197-30-4	Octocrylene	OC	0,85	vP	0,14	nM	T	143,5
	NS00077719	187393-00-6	Bemotrizinol	TinosorbS	0,61	vP	0,10	nM	T	143,5
	NS00013679	88122-99-0	2,4,6-Trianiino...	EHT	0,83	vP	0,11	nM	T	143,5
	NS00011474	118-60-5	Octisalate	EHS	0,90	vP	0,44	M	T	153,5
	NS00076467	1317-70-0	Anatase	TiO2	n.d.	-	n.d.	-	0	-6
	NS00074378	1317-80-2	Rutil	TiO2	n.d.	-	n.d.	-	0	-6
	NS00074402	13463-67-7	Titanium dioxide	TiO2	0,50	vP	n.d.	-	0	13
	NS00019490	302776-68-7	Diethylamino...	DHHB	0,84	vP	0,15	nM	T	143,5
	NS00006296	154702-15-5	Iscotrizinol	DBT	0,27	nP	n.d.	-	T	25,5
	NS00009551	118-56-9	Homosalate	HMS	0,82	vP	0,26	nM	T	143,5
	NS00004841	5466-77-3	Octinoxate	EHMC	0,84	vP	0,34	M	T	153,5
	NS00073564	155633-54-8	Drometrizole...	DTS	0,85	vP	0,10	nM	0	48
	NS00010386	27503-81-7	Ensulizole	PBSA	0,64	vP	0,42	M	T	153,5
	NS00004911	103597-45-1	bizotrizole	TinosorbM	0,83	vP	0,12	nM	T	143,5
	NS00073298	92761-26-7	Ecamsule	TDSA	0,83	vP	0,10	nM	0	48
	NS00001391	71617-10-2	Amiloxate	IMC	0,82	vP	0,40	M	T	153,5
	NS00074443	1314-13-2	Zinc oxide	ZnO	n.d.	-	n.d.	-	T	27
Other UV filters ^(e)	NS00002639	116242-27-4	Ethoxylated...	-	n.d.	-	n.d.	-	0	-6
	NS00000222	131-57-7	2-Hydroxy-4-...	-	0,82	vP	0,39	M	T	153,5
	NS00114736	180898-37-7	Bisdisulizol...	-	0,68	vP	n.d.	-	0	13
	NS00005726	21245-02-3	2-Ethylhexyl...	-	0,87	vP	0,31	nM	T	143,5
	NS00009581	4065-45-6	Sulisobenzone	-	0,83	vP	0,45	M	T	153,5
	NS00089185	52793-97-2	N,N,N-Trimethyl...	-	n.d.	-	n.d.	-	T	27
	NS00003490	55514-22-2	3,3'-(1,4-Phenyl...	-	0,74	vP	n.d.	-	T	67,5
	NS00013406	56039-58-8	alpha-(2-Oxob...	-	0,66	vP	n.d.	-	T	67,5
	NS00014087	5997-53-5	2-Phenylbenz...	-	0,70	vP	n.d.	-	T	67,5

Note: Benzotriazoles are in bold in lines shaded in grey. (a) P Score and M Score correspond to the average scenario, as presented in D5.1; (b) P Class. and M Class. correspond to the classification according to the average scenario, as presented in D5.1; (c) T class. corresponds to the robust scenario; (d) PS 15 (CAS No. 207574-74-1) is not included in the PROMISCES database; (e) 8 authorised UV-filters are not included in the PROMISCES database (CAS No.s 10020-01-6 ; 113783-61-2; 1419401-88-9; 158099-19-5; 207574-74-1; 31274-51-8; 919803-06-8; 6628-37-1)

5.5.3 Alternatives as corrosion inhibitors

The search for alternatives to benzotriazoles for applications as corrosion inhibitors is currently an active area of research, driven in particular by environmental concerns, as certain uses, such as aircraft de-icer fluids, are dispersive (see for instance Guo et al., 2022).

The relevance of replacing these compounds is supported by the analysis of results related to benzotriazoles identified for this application, which are presented in Table 16 below. It appears that 7 out of the 10 compounds are (at least) very persistent and very mobile (vPvM), or persistent, mobile, and toxic (PMT). Among the 3 other substances, 1 is toxic but persistence and mobility could not be assessed, and 2 are persistent, toxic and non-mobile.

Table 16: Analysis of alternatives of UV filters according to PROMISCES results

CAS No.	Cas No.	Name	Tonnage band	P score ^(a)	P class ^(b)	M score ^(a)	M class ^(b)	T class ^(c)	Global score
136-85-6	NS00008943	5-Methyl-1H-benzotriazole	0-10	0,61	vP	0,54	vM	0	147
2592-95-2	NS00007863	1-Hydroxybenzotriazole	10-100	0,63	vP	0,57	vM	T	163,5
25973-55-1	NS00010624	2-(2-Hydroxy-3,5-di-tert...	100-1 000	0,85	vP	0,17	nM	T	143,5
29385-43-1	NS00073843	Tolyltriazole	1 000-10 000	n.d.	-	n.d.	-	T	27
29878-31-7	NS00010509	4-Methyl-1,2,3-benzotriazole	-	0,63	vP	0,60	vM	T	163,5
3147-75-9	NS00008577	Octrizole	1 000-10 000	0,85	vP	0,35	M	T	153,5
4184-79-6	NS00008674	5,6-Dimethyl-1H-benzotriazole	-	0,63	vP	0,59	vM	T	163,5
94-97-3	NS00009697	5-Chlorobenzotriazole	-	0,60	vP	0,56	vM	T	163,5
95-14-7	NS00010261	1,2,3-Benzotriazole	1 000 – 10 000	0,63	vP	0,54	vM*	0	177
3896-11-5	NS00004466	Bumetrizole	1 000 – 10 000	0,82	vP	0,31	nM	T	143,5

Note: (a) P Score and M Score correspond to the average scenario, as presented in D5.1; (b) P Class. and M Class. correspond to the classification according to the average scenario, as presented in D5.1; (c) T class. corresponds to the robust scenario

*This classification for 1,2,3-Benzotriazole (CAS No. 95-14-7) as vM is confirmed by experimental data (robust scenario)

The search for corrosion inhibition solutions is a highly technical subject, largely dependent on the environments in which they are used (temperature, pH, and the liquids to which metals are exposed). Therefore, it was not possible within the timeframe of the study to carry out a comprehensive inventory of available solutions/substances and conduct a full analysis. For informational purposes, the different types of corrosion inhibitors are listed below (Răuță et al., 2025). Based on their chemical structure and functional groups, corrosion inhibitors can be classified as organic, inorganic, or hybrid inhibitors (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Classes of inhibitors (Source: Răuță et al., 2025)

- Inorganic inhibitors, including:
 - Anodic Corrosion Inhibitors or Chemical Passivators: These inhibitors function by forming a protective oxide layer on the metal surface, leading to passivation and reduction of the anodic reaction. Chromates and phosphates are included in this category.
 - Cathodic Corrosion Inhibitors: These compounds decrease the corrosion rate by precipitating on cathodic sites, thereby hindering the cathodic reaction. Examples include polyphosphates, zinc salts, ionic liquid monocationic and dicationic compounds, as well as hexylmethylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate ionic liquid. Other examples specific to certain environments are given in Răuță et al. (2025).
 - Mixed corrosion inhibitors: These inhibitors affect both anodic and cathodic reactions, often forming a protective film over the metal surface. Examples include silicates, Imidazolines in combination with phosphate compounds.

- Organic inhibitors: They are largely used in industries, including oil and gas, petrochemical, and marine applications. They can be classified as follows:
 - Synthetic organic corrosion inhibitors including benzotriazoles as presented in this report. Oxalamide (Carbamothiol) derivatives acting as corrosion inhibitors for copper, Imidazoline and Quinazolinone derivatives for steel in acidic conditions are other options. Surfactants are currently studied to develop biodegradable inhibitors (Lavanya et al., 2024).
 - Ionic liquids: Properties like low volatility, non-flammability, chemical stability, high solubility in polar solvents, and the ability to adsorb onto metallic surfaces, have made them popular in various industries. Common classes of ionic liquids include imidazolium, triazolium, thiazolium, phosphonium.
 - Bio-based inhibitors: Examples include Amino acids such as proline, histidine, and tryptophan; biopolymers ; and plant extracts such as those from neem or rosemary.

- Hybrid inhibitors (inorganic–organic): The combination of organic and inorganic inhibitors can allow to get the benefits of both categories of compounds. For instance, hybrid coatings combining metal oxides with organic polymers, like epoxy, exhibit high mechanical strength, enhanced adhesion, and increased resistance to environmental threats.

5.6 Conclusion

The work carried out in this section has provided key elements for assessing the relevance of substituting benzotriazoles.

More than a hundred compounds were identified and analysed using the methodologies and tools developed within the PROMISCES project. A thorough investigation of the uses of these substances was conducted.

Benzotriazoles are used in various industries and products, as UV absorbers (in plastics and coatings), UV filters in cosmetics and as corrosion inhibitors (in mechanical applications and household maintenance).

Regarding their application as UV absorbers, an analysis of potential alternatives was performed. The general conclusion, whether concerning applications in polymers, coatings, or cosmetics, is that currently available market alternatives tend to exhibit similar hazard profiles overall.

It would be useful to reduce certain uncertainties, for example by relying on new/other models to assess the persistence and mobility of substances. RIVM will assess whether the aquatic persistence model (see [Deliverable D2.6](#)) can be used in this regard. Furthermore, several approaches could help refine the prioritization of alternatives: working on the quantitative indicators (half-lives, etc.) instead of binary classifications (persistent/non-persistent), or integrating more nuanced toxicity criteria, may allow to discriminate more precisely the chemicals of concern.

However, based on the current state of knowledge, these findings suggest expanding the range of evaluated alternatives, either by developing tools to anticipate new chemical solutions or by designing substitution approaches that go beyond drop-in chemical substitution.

Regarding their use as corrosion inhibitors, the issue is technically too complex, and the information on possible alternatives is insufficiently consolidated to allow for a relevant inventory of options and for their analysis. However, the review of benzotriazoles used for this purpose clearly confirms the need to work toward their substitution. This appears to already be underway within industry, but an assessment based on a “safe and sustainable by design” approach has yet to be conducted. Cooperation between industry stakeholders and experts would probably be necessary to move this forward. A recent initiative in this direction took place in the Netherlands²⁵, involving dishwasher tablet manufacturers. We became aware of this work towards the end of the project. It will be interesting to analyse its results to further develop the present study.

²⁵https://open.rijkswaterstaat.nl/publish/pages/193154/benzotriazolonen_typen_toepassingen_zuivering_metingen_en_emissiebronnen.pdf (in Dutch)

6 General conclusion

Substitution is presented as being at the heart of European chemicals regulation. However, the effective and non-regrettable substitution of substances of concern remains a major challenge. One of the critical issues lies in the early identification of substances of concern and of safer alternatives, in order to provide industry with greater clarity and foresight regarding substances they may rely on in the future.

Within the framework of the PROMISCES project, and as presented in [Deliverable D5.1](#) and operationalised through the [DSF tool](#), over 120 000 substances were characterised against multiple criteria, including persistence, mobility, and toxicity. The aim of this report was to present three distinct approaches based on these results, each offering insights into the substitution of PMTs.

The first approach explores the use of data from REACH registration dossiers. It confirms that PMT concerns are not limited to specific sectors or product categories. However, it also highlights that existing use-related information is currently insufficient to support robust prioritisation for substitution.

The second approach is based on the NORMAN database, which groups substances by shared technical functions. Focusing on surfactants, the analysis shows that hundreds of substances may warrant prioritisation for substitution, depending on the robustness of the assessment scenarios. While modelled data offer valuable insights, their use requires careful scrutiny, as conservative assumptions may result in an unmanageably large number of substances being flagged as of concern. This approach did not identify safer alternatives, an unexpected result warranting further investigation.

Finally, the third approach combines the PROMISCES project data with a traditional literature-based assessment of uses and alternatives. The case of benzotriazoles is examined in detail. For several uses, we conducted an analysis of alternatives. One general conclusion is that currently available market alternatives tend to exhibit similar hazard profiles overall. These findings suggest expanding the range of evaluated alternatives, either by developing tools to anticipate new chemical solutions or by designing substitution approaches that go beyond drop-in chemical substitution. However, it would be necessary to reduce certain uncertainties and investigate quantitative approaches for a more robust conclusion, for example by relying on new/other models to assess the persistence and mobility of substances.

In the case of use as corrosion inhibitors, the work reminded that substitution is a highly technical matter, for which identifying the substances, their hazard properties, or even use data alone is not sufficient. Cooperation between industry stakeholders and experts would probably be necessary.

Overall, this report underscores the need for further research at the intersection of data science, (eco)toxicology and economics to enhance the effectiveness of substitution strategies. It also highlights important gaps in data availability and usability that hinder the identification of both substances of concern and safer alternatives.

7 References

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8 Annexes

Table 17 : List of Sources within the SusDat database and associated uses

Source number	Source name	Details	Name in NORMAN	Use acronym	Retained as use category
S1	MASSBANK NORMAN	Compounds in MassBank	Unknown	UN	
S2	STOFFIDENT HSWT/LFU	STOFF-IDENT Database of Water-Relevant Substances	Drinking water chemicals	DW	
S3	NORMANCT15	NORMAN Collaborative Trial Targets and Suspects	Unknown	UN	
S4	UJIBADE	University of Jaume I	Unknown	UN	
S5	KWRSJERPS	KWR Drinking Water Suspect List	Drinking water chemicals	DW	
S6	ITNANTIBIOTIC	Antibiotic List: ITN MSCA ANSWER	Pharma	PHARMA	yes
S7	EAWAGSURF	Eawag Surfactants Suspect List	Surfactants	SURF	yes
S8	ATHENSUS	University of Athens Surfactants and Suspects List	Surfactants	SURF	yes
S9	PFASTRIER	PFAS Suspect List: fluorinated substances	PFAS	PFAS	
S10	SWISSPHARMA	Pharmaceutical List with Consumption Data	Pharmaceuticals	PHARMA	yes
S11	SWISSPEST	Swiss Insecticides, Fungicides and TPs	Agrochemicals	PPP	yes
S12	NORMANEWS	NormaNEWS for Retrospective Screening of New Emerging Contaminants	Unknown	UN	
S13	EUCOSMETICS	Combined Inventory of Ingredients Employed in Cosmetic Products (2000/2006)	Personal care products	PCP	yes
S14	SFISHFLUORO	PFAS Highly Fluorinated Substances List: KEMI	PFAS	PFAS	
S15	NORMANPRI	NORMAN Priority List	Unknown	UN	
S16	FRENCHLIST	French Monitoring List	Unknown	UN	
S17	KEMIMARKET	KEMI Market List	Unknown	UN	
S18	TSCASURF	TSCA Surfactants	Surfactants	SURF	yes
S19	MZCLOUDDB	mzCloud Compounds	Unknown	UN	
S20	BISPHENOLS	Bisphenols	Plastic additives	PLAST	yes
S21	UATHTARGETS	University of Athens Target List	Unknown	UN	
S22	EPACONS	US EPA Consumer Product Suspect List	Unknown	UN	
S23	EIUBASURF	Surfactant Suspect List from EI and UBA	Surfactants	SURF	yes
S24	HUMANNEUROTOX	List of Human Neurotoxins	Human neurotoxins	HUTOX	
S25	OECDPFAS	List of PFAS from the OECD	PFAS	PFAS	
S26	MYCOTOXINS	List of Mycotoxins from AAFC	Natural toxins	NATOX	

S27	KWRSJERPS2	Extended Suspect List from Sjerps et al (KWRSJERPS)	Unknown	UN	
S28	EUBIOCIDES	Biocides from the NORMAN Priority List	Biocides	BIOCID	yes
S29	PHYTOTOXINS	Toxic Plant Phytotoxin (TPPT) Database	Natural toxins	NATOX	
S30	PHENANTIOX	A list of Phenolic Antioxidants from KEMI and NILU	Personal care products	PCP	yes
S31	WRTMSD	Wiley Registry of Tandem Mass Spectral Data, MSforID	Unknown	UN	
S32	REACH2017	>68,600 REACH Chemicals	REACH chemicals	REACH	
S33	SOLUTIONSMLOS	Chemicals used for Modelling in SOLUTIONS	Unknown	UN	
S34	EXPOSOMEXPL	Biomarkers from Exposome Explorer	Unknown	UN	
S35	INDOORCT16	Indoor Environment Substances from 2016 Collaborative Trial	Indoor environment substances	INDOOR	
S36	UBAPMT	Potential Persistent, Mobile and Toxic (PMT) substances	Persistent, mobile and toxic	PMT	
S37	LITMINEDNEURO	Neurotoxicants from literature mining PubMed	Human neurotoxins	HUTOX	
S38	SOLNSLMCTPS	SOLUTIONS Predicted Transformation Products by LMC	Unknown	UN	
S39	KEMIWWSUS	Wastewater Suspect List based on Swedish Product Data	Unknown	UN	
S40	ALGALTOX	Algal toxins list from CompTox	Natural toxins	NATOX	
S41	CCL4	CCL 4 Chemical Candidate List	Unknown	UN	
S42	HDXNOEX	Hydrogen Deuterium Exchange (HDX) Standard Set	Unknown	UN	
S43	NEUROTOXINS	Neurotoxicants Collection from Public Resources	Human neurotoxins	HUTOX	
S44	STATINS	Statins Collection from Public Resources	Pharmaceuticals	PHARMA	yes
S45	SYNTHCANNAB	Synthetic Cannabinoids	Unknown	UN	
S46	PFASNTREV19	List of PFAS reported in Non-Target HRMS Studies (Liu et al 2019)	PFAS	PFAS	
S47	ECHAPLASTICS	A list from the Plastic Additives Initiative Mapping Exercise by ECHA	Plastic additives	PLAST	yes
S48	CCPDBLISTA	Database of Chemicals associated with Plastic Packaging (CPPdb)	Plastic additives	PLAST	yes
S49	CCPDBLISTB	Database of Chemicals associated with Plastic Packaging (CPPdb)	Plastic additives	PLAST	yes
S50	CCSCOMPEND	The Unified Collision Cross Section (CCS) Compendium	Unknown	UN	
S51	WRIGCHRMS	GC-HRMS target list of WRI	Unknown	UN	
S52	THSMOKE	Thirdhand Smoke (THS) Compounds	Smoke compounds	SMOKE	
S53	UFZWANATARG	Target Compounds from UFZ WANA	Unknown	UN	
S54	EFSAPRI	European Food Safety Authority Priority Substances	Food contact chemicals	FOODC	yes

S55	ZINC15PHARMA	>8600 Pharmaceuticals from ZINC15	Pharmaceuticals	PHARMA	yes
S56	UOATARGPHARMA	Target Pharmaceutical/Drug List from University of Athens	Pharmaceuticals	PHARMA	yes
S57	GREEKPHARMA	Suspect Pharmaceuticals from the National Organization of Medicine, Greece	Pharmaceuticals	PHARMA	yes
S58	PSYCHOCANNAB	Synthetic Cannabinoids and Psychoactive Compounds	Drugs of abuse	DOA	
S59	NPINESCT	Natural Product Insecticides	Biocides	BIOCID	yes
S60	SWISSPEST19	Swiss Pesticides and Metabolites from Kiefer et al 2019	Plant protection products	PPP	yes
S61	UJICCSLIB	Collision Cross Section (CCS) Library from UJI	Unknown	UN	
S62	NORMANEWS2	NormaNEWS2: Retrospective Screening of New Emerging Contaminants	Unknown	UN	
S63	UBADWGW	Substances Detected in Drinking (DW) or Groundwater (GW)	Drinking water chemicals	DW	
S64	NATOXAQ	NaToxAq: Natural Toxins and Drinking Water Quality - From Source to Tap	Drinking water chemicals; Natural toxins	DW; NATOX	
S65	UATHTARGETSGC	University of Athens GC-APCI-HRMS Target List	Unknown	UN	
S66	EAWAGTPS	Parent-Transformation Product Pairs from Eawag	Unknown	UN	
S67	TBUTYLPHENOLS	List of tert-butyl phenols from KEMI	Industrial chemicals	IND	
S68	HSDBTPS	Transformation Products Extracted from HSDB Content in PubChem	Unknown	UN	
S69	LUXPEST	Pesticide Screening List for Luxembourg	Plant protection products	PPP	yes
S70	EISUSGCEIMS	Environmental Institute GC-EI-MS suspect list	Unknown	UN	
S71	CECScreen	HBM4EU CECscreen: Screening List for Chemicals of Emerging Concern	Unknown	UN	
S72	NTUPHTW	Pharmaceutically Active Substances Suspect List from National Taiwan University	Pharmaceuticals	PHARMA	yes
S73	METXBIODB	Metabolite Reaction Database from BioTransformer	Unknown	UN	
S74	REFTPS	Transformation Products and Reactions from Literature	Unknown	UN	
S75	CYANOMETDB	Comprehensive database of secondary metabolites from cyanobacteria	Natural toxins	NATOX	
S76	LUXPHARMA	Pharmaceuticals Marketed in Luxembourg	Pharmaceuticals	PHARMA	yes
S77	FCCDB	Food Contact Chemicals Database v5.0	Food contact chemicals	FOODC	yes
S78	SLUPESTTPS	Pesticides and TPs from SLU, Sweden	Plant protection products	PPP	
S79	UACCSCEC	Collision Cross Section (CCS) Library from UAntwerp	Unknown	UN	
S80	PFASGLUEGE	Overview of PFAS Uses	PFAS	PFAS	
S81	THSTPS	Thirdhand Smoke Specific Metabolites	Smoke compounds	SMOKE	

S82	EAWAGPMT	PMT Suspect List from Eawag	Persistent, mobile and toxic	PMT	
S83	CCL5	Contaminant Candidate List CCL 5 (Draft)	Unknown	UN	
S84	UFZHSFPMT	PMT Suspect List from UFZ and HSF	Persistent, mobile and toxic	PMT	
S85	MICROCYSTINS	MICROCYSTINS from CyanoMetDB	Natural toxins	NATOX	
S86	TATTOOINK	TATTOOINK as per EU regulation 2020/2081	Personal care products	PCP	yes
S87	CHLORINETPS	List of chlorination byproducts of 137 CECs and small disinfection byproducts	Unknown	UN	
S88	UBABIOCIDES	List of Prioritized Biocides from UBA	Biocides	BIOCID	yes
S89	PRORISKPFAS	List of PFAS Compiled from NORMAN SusDat	PFAS	PFAS	
S90	ZEROPMBOX1	ZeroPM Box 1 Substances	Persistent, mobile and toxic	PMT	
S91	CECTOYS	Chemicals of Emerging Concern (CECs) in plastic toys	Children's products	CHILD	yes
S92	FLUOROPHARMA	List of 340 ATC classified fluoro-pharmaceuticals	Pharmaceuticals	PHARMA	yes
S93	CECMOUTHING	Chemicals of Emerging Concern (CECs) in children's mouthing exposure	Children's products	CHILD	yes
S94	FLUROPEST	List of 423 FRAC/HRAC/IRAC classified fluoro-agrochemicals	Agrochemicals	BIOCID	yes
S95	PFASANEXCH	PFAS List from the NORMAN PFAS Analytical Exchange Activity	PFAS	PFAS	
S96	ECIPFAS	Updatable List to add PFAS Structures to Public Resources from ECI (UniLu)	PFAS	PFAS	
S97	UBABPAALT	List of Bisphenol A Alternatives from UBA	Unknown	UN	
S98	TIRECHEM	Tire-Related Chemicals in Environment from Literature	Unknown	UN	
S99	ANSESEDC	List of potential endocrine disrupting compounds (EDCs) from ANSES	Endocrine disruptors	EDCs	
S100	PFASREACH	List of PFAS identified in REACH 2019	PFAS	PFAS	
S101	MTMDUST	List of chemicals characterized in indoor dust samples	Indoor environment substances	INDOOR	
S102	PARCPFAS	List of PFAS from PARC WP4	PFAS	PFAS	
S103	NORMANUVCB	NORMAN Dataset of Curated UVCB Mappings	Unknown	UN	
S104	UKVETMED	UK Veterinary Medicines Directorate's List	Pharmaceuticals	PHARMA	yes
S105	P65CHEM	Californian Proposition 65 warning list of chemicals	Unknown	UN	
S106	AQUALity19	EU AQUALity's water analysis list 2019	Unknown	UN	
S107	AQUALity20	EU AQUALity's water analysis list 2020	Unknown	UN	
S108	SINLIST	SIN (Substitute It Now) list of hazardous chemicals by ChemSec	Unknown	UN	
S109	PARCEDC	List of 7074 potential endocrine disrupting compounds (EDCs) by PARC T4.2	Endocrine disruptors	EDCs	

S110	DUTCHUSE	Dutch Prioritized Chemical Use Categories	Unknown	UN	
S111	PMTPFAS	Fluorine-containing Compounds in PMT Suspect Lists	PFAS	PFAS	
S112	FCCMIGEX	List of Migrating & Extractable Food Contact Chemicals (FCCmigex) by FPF	Food contact chemicals	FOODC	yes
S113	SWISSPHARMA24	2024 Swiss Pharmaceutical List with Metabolites	Pharmaceuticals	PHARMA	yes
S114	SLUAMTPS	Antimicrobial Transformation Products from SLU	Personal care products	PCP	yes
S115	EIEQSDWLGC	EQS Directive and Watch List for GC from Environmental Institute	Drinking water chemicals	DW	
S116	REFCCS	Collision Cross Section (CCS) Values from Literature	Unknown	UN	
S117	PFASFCCDB	140 PFAS from FCCdb	PFAS	PFAS	
S118	PFASFCCMIGEX	68 PFAS in Migrating & Extractable Food Contact Chemicals (FCCmigex)	PFAS	PFAS	
S119	PLASTCHEM	List of Plastchem database chemicals	Plastic additives	PLAST	yes
S120	DUSTCT2024	Substances from Second NORMAN Collaborative Dust Trial	Indoor environment substances	INDOOR	

Table 18 : Description for the different Sectors of Use as defined by the REACH regulation

	Sector of Use Description
SU 1	Agriculture, forestry and fishing
SU 2a	Mining (without offshore industries)
SU 2b	Offshore industries
SU 4	Manufacture of food products
SU 5	Manufacture of textiles, leather, fur
SU 6a	Manufacture of wood and wood products
SU 6b	Manufacture of pulp, paper and paper products
SU 7	Printing and reproduction of recorded media
SU 8	Manufacture of bulk, large scale chemicals (including petroleum products)
SU 9	Manufacture of fine chemicals
SU 10	Formulation [mixing] of preparations and/or re-packaging (excluding alloys)
SU 11	Manufacture of rubber products
SU 12	Manufacture of plastics products, including compounding and conversion
SU 13	Manufacture of other non-metallic mineral products, e.g. plasters, cement
SU 14	Manufacture of basic metals, including alloys
SU 15	Manufacture of fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment
SU 16	Manufacture of computer, electronic and optical products, electrical equipment
SU 17	General manufacturing, e.g. machinery, equipment, vehicles, other transport equipment
SU 18	Manufacture of furniture
SU 19	Building and construction work
SU 20	Health services
SU 23	Electricity, steam, gas water supply and sewage treatment
SU 24	Scientific research and development

Table 19 : Description for the different Product Categories as defined by the REACH regulation

	Description
PC 0	Other
PC 1	Adhesives, sealants
PC 2	Adsorbents
PC 3	Air care products
PC 4	Anti-freeze and de-icing products
PC 7	Base mettals and alloys
PC 8	Biocidal products (e.g. disinfectants, pest control)
PC 9a	Coatings and paints, thinners, paint removes
PC 9b	Fillers, putties, plasters, modelling clay
PC 9c	Finger paints
PC 11	Explosives
PC 12	Fertilizers
PC 13	Fuels
PC 14	Metal surface treatment products
PC 15	Non-metal-surface treatment products
PC 16	Heat transfer fluids
PC 17	Hydraulic fluids
PC 18	Ink and toners
PC 19	Intermediate
PC 20	Products such as ph-regulators, flocculants, precipitants, neutralisation agents
PC 21	Laboratory chemicals
PC 23	Leather treatment products
PC 24	Lubricants, greases, release products
PC 25	Metal working fluids
PC 26	Paper and board treatment products
PC 27	Plan protection products
PC 28	Perfumes, fragrances
PC 29	Pharmaceuticals
PC 30	Photo-chemicals
PC 31	Polishes and wax blends
PC 32	Polymer preparations and compounds
PC 33	Semiconductors
PC 34	Textile dyes, and impregnating products
PC 35	Washing and cleaning products
PC 36	Water softener
PC 37	Water treatment chemicals'
PC 38	Welding and soldering products, flux products
PC 39	Cosmetics, personal care products
PC 40	Extraction agents
PC 41	Oil and gas exploration or production products
PC 42	Electrolytes for batteries